

University of Wah
Quality Education for All

9th Multi Disciplinary Student Research International Conference (MDSRIC-2024)

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CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

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Office of the Research, Innovation
 & Commercialization (ORIC)

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PREFACE

It is indeed a matter of great satisfaction for the Commercialization (ORIC) at the University of Wah to present to you the Abstract Book of the 8th Multi-Disciplinary Student Research International Conference (MDSRIC-9) organized on 16-17 October 2024.

MDSRIC is a flagship event of the University of Wah organized annually before the closing of each calendar year. It invites unpublished research papers on topics covered under the broad areas of Basic Sciences, Management Sciences, Social Sciences, Engineering and Computer Science.

MDSRIC provides a forum for students to reignite their passion for their field and inculcate critical thinking skills. It creates opportunities for participants including students and professionals from academia and industry to network and interact with colleagues from different disciplines via presenting their research findings and through mutual interactions, brainstorming sessions, and fusion of ideas, etc.

MDSRIC is equally beneficial for faculty as it provides new insights into the best pedagogical practices and opportunity for collaboration with fellow educators and stay up to date with the latest trends and research in their fields. The conference is well-aligned with the vision of GoP to promote development of an enlightened and prospering nation by reinforcing knowledge economy along with a focus on equitable and quality learning.

The call for papers for the conference was initiated well in time and there was an overwhelming response from all around the country. A large number of research papers were submitted out of which around 90 abstracts have been accepted by the technical review committee for presentation in the conference and publication in the conference proceedings.

We thank the University of Wah for financing this conference that serves the purpose of promoting research in Pakistan. We also thank all the participants, students, reviewers and organizers for their participation and support during the conference. Organizing such an event is a challenging task and we were fortunate enough to have several colleagues and students who worked tirelessly behind the scenes to ensure the success of the conference.

Conference Chair
MDSRIC-2024

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KEYNOTE

TALKS

Disruptive HR & Digital Economy

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ABSTRACT

Numerous academic scholars, thought leaders, and practitioners have debated the impact of digital transformation on business and society. The commentaries on disruptive HR and its consequentialist effects on the economy have invited both excitement and suspicion (Kraus et al., 2021; Bonnet and Westerman, 2020). An overwhelming focus of discussions around this topic have largely centered on questions of job loss, machines replacing HR, skills for the future, etc. (WEF 2022) without offering much to moving education agenda forward, as to what ought to be done to ensure a reasoned response from academic providers of the new economy?

Taking into account the intersection of digital disruption and human resources, the speaker will share some global numbers about job market risks posed by rapid digitalization, and its implications for social inclusion or exclusion. Drawing upon the advances in the information age, World Economic Forum, and McKinsey reports, education experiences and resilience responses, the talk will cover the possible opportunities, employment equilibrium (or disequilibrium), and future scenarios of what might happen and what can be done by academic policy shapers in the wake of impending challenges.

The Role of Research in Business and Academia

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ABSTRACT

Research, theoretical as well as empirical, has a critically role to play in modern-day business, academia, and policy design and its implementation, providing sound foundation for effective, efficient, and informed decision-making, scientific advancements and innovations, sustainable development and growth, and human- and environment-friendly corporate practices. On the one hand, it helps in expanding the frontier of knowledge and a deeper and better understanding of very complex real life problems and phenomena. On the other hand, it provides data-driven insights that enable businesses and policy-makers to make effective decisions regarding investments, productions, growth, and risk management strategies. Research plays a vital role in identifying new and more profitable investment opportunities, improving efficiency and productivity, reducing costs and risk exposures. Academic research results in development of new theories, advancements in methodological methods, sophisticated and more relevant framework and empirical models, and improvements in the way research is conducted and analyzed. Research activities are very important for cognitive development, fostering critical thinking, promoting analytical skills, and promoting problem solving in both business and academia.

Role of AI in Agriculture and Food Security

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ABSTRACT

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in agriculture is set to transform the industry and play a critical role in addressing global food security challenges. As the world faces the dual pressures of climate change and a rapidly growing population, AI offers innovative solutions to optimize agricultural practices, enhance productivity, and ensure sustainable resource management. Through the use of machine learning, predictive analytics, and autonomous systems, AI is enabling farmers to make data-driven decisions, leading to more efficient crop management, reduced resource wastage, and improved resilience against environmental stressors. AI-driven technologies are reshaping the agricultural landscape from precision farming and automated harvesting to climate-resilient crop development and advanced supply chain management. AI has the potential not only to boost agricultural output but also to create a more sustainable and secure global food system. By embracing AI, the agriculture sector can address current and future challenges, ensuring that we can feed the world while preserving the planet for future generations.

TALYS Nuclear Reaction code usage in Nuclear Reactions and Nuclear Models

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ABSTRACT

TALYS nuclear-reaction code is a Fortran based nuclear code used to simulate nuclear reactions for heavier than lithium target nucleus using n, p, d, t, ^3He , α particles and γ ray could use as projectile in the energy region of 1keV–1GeV. Many nuclear models can be tested in this code as theory allows. In this study, information about nuclear models and reactions with application via Talys nuclear reaction code are given.

Role of STI and Social sciences in achieving sustainable development goals and quality of life

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ABSTRACT

An effective education system, inculcates three qualities in a University/College graduate, which include Confidence, Creativity and Character, where Social Sciences have very important role to play. It has been observed that an education system which provides broad-based education, is better prepared for producing such graduates. It is not surprising that more than 50 % of Nobel laureates of the World are graduates of Colleges of Liberal Arts, well known to provide broad-based education. In addition to routine teaching, a university Teacher/Professor is engaged in scholarly work/research, which requires collaboration. High impact publications are emerged usually from a broad-based collaboration, not only within the university but also at national/international level. This means that social skills required to lead a research team, are as important as technological skills. Recent research shows that those who are socially active, live longer.

Similarly, nations are heavily dependent on each other to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In September 2015, the UN member states approved an ambitious agenda to address the poverty, the pursuit of equity and the protection of the planet in the form of 17 SDGs, which are mostly interdependent. We all wish to have good quality of life, which is heavily dependent on different indicators such as Physical and mental health, Access to education, Freedom of expression, Clean and secure living environment and Sound economics but what about a situation when: We are healthy, but we are poor and don't have access to education? OR We have a secure income, but the air that we breath is unclean and there is no freedom of expression OR We have freedom of expression, with clean/safe environment but we can't feed our family? Obviously, we need to have all of these things, only then we can say that we are having a good quality of life.

This presentation will emphasize on the significance and interconnectivity of three pillars of sustainable development (Economic, Environmental and Social), where each individual as well as all nations have a role to play in achieving SDGs and hence, for a good quality of life, true understanding of Islam is very important which focuses on building a prosperous, healthy and peaceful society.

Solitons, A Permanent Wave

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ABSTRACT

A wave is defined as a disturbance that travels through a medium, transporting energy as it moves. Unlike other waves, soliton maintains its shape even after collision with other solitons. Solitons have many applications in Mathematics, Physics, Biology etc. They are the solutions of nonlinear partial differential equations. Equations that admit soliton solutions have profound mathematical structures and properties. One of the key properties of these equations is that they have an infinite number of conservation laws.

Human centric intelligent planning and scheduling systems for manufacturing and service industries for Industry 5.0

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ABSTRACT

Fourth industrial revolution merged systems engineering and information technology to make systems intelligent and smart using industrial internet of things (IIOT), data driven methods, cloud computing, intelligent manufacturing and digital twin concepts. Since, manufacturing or service industries involve humans working in collaboration with machines and equipment. Therefore, planning and scheduling decisions considering industry 4.0 concepts without involving human centricity may not give completely realistic decisions. There are three main pillars which are added by European Commission in the systems including human centricity, resilient and sustainability to evolve Industry 5.0. These pillars are significant to provide safe and supportive environment to promote collaborative and safe environment for manual workers, provide robust, self-adaptive, intelligent, flexible and agile environment to resist disruptions and provide green environment by reducing waste, increasing resource efficiency, reducing cost, increasing economic growth for societal well-being through lean and green strategies and management. Recent planning and scheduling systems are evolving based on Industry 4.0 concepts and there is need to include human centric, robust, self-adaptive and lean and green system for intelligent planning and scheduling in production and service systems. Therefore, current research shows human centric intelligent planning and scheduling system for manufacturing and service industries for industry 5.0.

Recent Advances in Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Technologies

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ABSTRACT

The solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) is one of the most important in fuel cell technologies which produce electricity directly from gaseous fuel with an oxidant in an efficient and environmentally way. Although there are many researches about, yttria stabilized zirconia (YSZ) has been widely used as an electrolyte material in SOFCs. However, YSZ requires high operating temperatures (1000°C). This high operating temperature causes many problems and economical expenses. We need to increase the operation temperature of the SOFCs to the intermediate temperature (IT) range (500–750°C).

Bi₂O₃ based electrolytes are good candidate for achieving intermediate temperature electrolytes in SOFCs. Bi₂O₃ ternary system sample materials were synthesized using solid state reaction method sintering each of them. Structural and electrical properties of these electrolyte samples for solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) have been evaluated by means of XRD, TG / DTA, SEM and four-point probe method. Structural behaviors of the phases were investigated by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). Thermal behavior and thermal stability of the phases were investigated by differential thermal analysis (TG / DTA). Surface and grain properties of the related phases were determined by SEM analysis. The temperature dependence of the electrical properties of δ -phase of solid solution samples were measured by four-point probe d.c. conductivity method.

The main aims of this study to determine δ -phase of bismuth trioxide ternary system and the temperature dependence of the electrical transport properties. For this purpose, this research is to determine the stable crystal ternary structures with an adequate dopant amount which has higher electrical conductivity and better stabilities The samples which synthesized in our studies can be used in diverse industrial applications such as electrolytes of the intermediate temperature solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC).

Keywords: Solid Oxide Fuel Cells, Intermediate Temperature, Bi₂O₃ ternary system, Electrical conductivity.

Allowed and First Forbidden Beta Decays

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ABSTRACT

The study of nuclear beta decay provides information both about the nature of the weak interaction and about the structure of nuclear wave functions. There are two types of transitions involved in nuclear β -decay: allowed and forbidden, depending on the angular momentum (l) of the emitted leptons relative to the nucleus. The allowed transition corresponds to $l=0$ while $l > 0$ ($l=1$) corresponds to the first forbidden transition. The properties of nuclear beta decays are in most cases dominated by the allowed transition, while the (first) forbidden transition plays a crucial and decisive role in many cases. In the present study, the allowed and first-forbidden beta transition properties of some nuclei that make a significant contribution to the r -process were calculated with the schematic model approach in the framework pn-Quasi Random Phase Approximation (pn-QRPA), and the results were compared with the corresponding experimental data.

Keywords— Allowed and First-forbidden transitions, Schematic model, pn-QRPA

BASIC SCIENCES

Investigation of β -Decay Properties of Neutron-rich Ge Nuclei

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the half-lives, GT strength distributions and $\log ft$ values using proton-neutron quasi random phase approximation (pn-QRPA) model on Ge isotopes in the mass region $A = 67-80$. We used RPA equation in both channels particle-particle (pp) and particle-hole (ph) by employing deformed Nilsson basis. We adopted the nuclear deformation of these nuclei from the Finite Range Droplet Model (FRDM). Later on, the computed deformation values were used as input parameter in pn-QRPA model with separable interaction to calculate the β -Decay properties and electron/positron capture rates of these nuclei. The predicted β decay half-lives are within a factor of 2 compared to the measured values. It was concluded that the FRDM computed deformation values provided the best calculated half-lives. Under the high temperature and density conditions present in the cores of massive stars, the calculated pn-QRPA stellar rates can be up to an order of magnitude greater than the rates from the independent shell model. These findings may be useful for modeling the late-stage evolution of massive stars.

Keywords: β -decay half-lives, GT strength distribution, pn-QRPA, Electron capture rates, Stellar rates

Investigation of β -Decay Properties near magic number $N = 82$

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ABSTRACT

The r-process is responsible for producing approximately 50% of the heavy elements beyond iron. The β -decay properties of waiting-point nuclei are essential for determining the r-process path. In this study, we examine the β -decay properties of neutron-rich nuclei with $N = 81$ and 82 and Z ranging from 42 to 49. We employ the proton-neutron Quasiparticle Random Phase Approximation (pn-QRPA) model to compute Gamow-Teller transitions, β -decay half-lives, neutron emission probabilities, and stellar rates for these neutron-rich isotones.

We compare our results with previous calculations and measured data where available. Our model reproduced 100% (82%) terrestrial β -decay half-lives within a factor 10 (2). Our model predictions are in decent agreement with the experimental data. We present the stellar weak rates of these neutron-rich nuclei for the first time. The reported stellar rates could prove useful for r-process nucleosynthesis calculations and simulations of late-time stellar evolution.

Keywords: β -decay rates; Gamow-Teller strength distributions; Neutron emission probabilities; pn-QRPA

Study the β -decay charge-changing transitions of Odd-A nuclei in mass range $A = 125-141$ using deformed pn-QRPA

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ABSTRACT

The r-process abundance peaks of isotopes at mass numbers 80, 130 and 195 and the corresponding time scales are determined by β -decay half-lives. In past, number of attempts using different approaches to study the β -decay characteristics of many neutron-rich nuclei, it seems a formidable task to approach the high-mass exotic nuclei around the neutron drip-line by terrestrial experiments. In this scenario, a reliable theoretical model is in order that could reproduce the measured half-lives and predict the unknown. pn-QRPA is a reliable theoretical approach used to computed and predict the β -decay charge changing transitions. In the current study, we investigate the β -decay properties for nuclei in the vicinity of mass range 130 using the pn-QRPA model. We choose odd-A nuclei ($^{125-131}\text{Cs}$, $^{127-133}\text{Ba}$, $^{129-135}\text{La}$ and $^{133-141}\text{Xe}$) to investigate the β -decay properties. We calculate $\log ft$ values, Gamow-Teller (GT) strength distributions, branching ratios, partial and total half-lives as well as stellar rates for the selected nuclei. We compare our results with measured data and previous calculations wherever available. Our model reproduced well the low-lying GT transitions up to 3 MeV in the daughter. Our GT calculations fulfilled the Ikeda sum rule. Our model was able to reproduce β -decay half-lives within a factor 2 of measured half-lives for more than 75% of the cases. The stellar weak rates Cs, Ba and La isotopes increased with increasing core temperatures and densities. For the Xe isotopes, the stellar β rates decreased by orders of magnitude with increasing core densities and created impact only at high core temperature values in excess of 10 GK. The reported results can prove useful for simulators working on nucleosynthesis calculations.

Adsorption Materials for the Efficient Removal of Methylene Blue from Wastewater: A Review

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ABSTRACT

A significant environmental issue has arisen as a result of some enterprises' recent releases of wastewater into the environment that contains high quantities of dyes (i.e. contamination of soil, groundwater, and surface water etc.). The sudden development of the textile industry has led to a concerning scenario where chemicals, such as dyes, are left in treated wastewater, further damaging the environment. Recent research has shown that the use of activated carbon is a very effective technique for eliminating methylene blue (MB) from wastewater. A beneficial source of bio-waste for MB sweeping includes wood scraps, animal-based food waste, and crop residue, as they are extremely effective, reusable, and have solid adsorption capacities. This review paper examines the properties of biowaste-based adsorbents for dye removal, focusing on their efficiency and processing techniques. It also discusses regeneration procedures, financial difficulties, and post-sorption material valuation. The high cost of commercially available activated carbon restricts its supply; hence, researchers are searching for affordable and unexpected sources for adsorbents. This overview provides a comprehensive understanding of recent developments in biowaste-derived adsorbents, emphasizing the need for inexpensive adsorbents for large-scale system optimization.

Keywords: Adsorption, Methylene Blue, Wastewater treatment, Adsorbents, Removal efficiency. Activated Carbon, Dyes, Environment.

NTF Zero Optimization for Noise Shaping in Delta-Sigma Modulator

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents comparative analysis of zero optimization technique for single-loop active with passive delta-sigma modulator for in-band noise reduction in cascade of integrated with multiple feedback (CIFB) as well as cascade of integrator with multiple feedforward (CIFF). The order of the modulator exploited for different level of the quantizer for the performance comparison. The effect of quantization noise reduction due to NTF zero optimization in active as well as passive delta-sigma modulator studied. The signal transfer function (STF) and NTF of the different modulator presented with and without NTF zero optimization technique. The operational amplifier (op-amp) with open loop DC gain also simulated with and without NTF zero optimization technique. The reduced DC gain causes higher in-band quantization noise. The op-amp slew-rate is also simulated for the modulator performance. The out-of-band gain of the modulators is also exploited for better noise reduction for higher order modulators. The CIFB topology was implemented due to higher stability of multiple feedback and zero optimization approach. High oversampling ratio (OSR) utilized, due to very small bandwidth requirement low as well as high bandwidth applications. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for different OSR as well as modulator order exploited. For the case of ideal 4th order modulator with 4-bit quantizer, SNR of 91dB with NTF zero optimization technique while without NTF zero optimization technique is 79.5dB

Keywords: NTF, STF, Delta-Sigma Modulator, CIFF, CIFB.

Two-Stage Operational Amplifier Design for Biomedical Applications

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a single-stage as well as two-stage operational amplifier design in 55nm CMOS Technology. An operational amplifier is the basic building block for the analog circuit. The low power biomedical instrumentation demanded a low power operational amplifier. The first stage uses a folded cascode amplifier, with switched-capacitor common mode feedback. While the second stage uses a common source amplifier with switched-capacitor common mode feedback. The frequency compensation employed to ensure the stability of the two-stage amplifier. The aspect ratio of the operational amplifier is adjusted to meet the open loop DC gain requirement. The op-amp is simulated in the Cadence simulation environment for high accuracy. The first stage op-amp design does not have much higher current as compared to the second stage. The second stage drives much higher current. The amplifier is simulated for different process corners and DC, AC and Transient analysis. The two-stage op-amp having first stage as folded-cascode and second stage as common source amplifier can achieve DC gain of 35 dB and GBW of 500 MHz at supply voltage of 1-V in nanometer CMOS technology.

Keywords: Operational Amplifier, open-loop gain, slew-rate, folded-cascode.

50MS Sample & Hold Circuit Design in Nanometer CMOS Technology

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents sample and hold circuit design at supply voltage of 1-V in nanometer CMOS technology. The precision of the sample and hold circuit is 10-bit with differential output voltage of 0.5-V, the differential input voltage is 1-V with gain of 2. The circuit consists of switched-capacitor based circuit with high open-loop DC gain of the operational amplifier. The aspect ratio of each of the transistors is adjusted to meet the higher gain requirement. The open-loop DC gain simulated using AC analysis in the cadence environment. The circuit employs the two-stage high gain operational amplifier with common source boosters. The switched-capacitor circuit employed in the common mode feedback circuit of the operational amplifier design. The capacitors values are adjusted in each of the common mode feedback circuit. As this op-amp has two stages, two different common mode feedback circuits are employed. The size of the switches for the case of common mode feedback circuit is very small considering the stability of the amplifier. The switches for the sample and hold circuits are also optimized for better performance. Considering the gain of the 2 for the sample of hold circuit, the ratio of sampling capacitor as well as integration capacitor are chosen to meet the required gain. The circuit simulation in Cadence virtuoso environment shows the sample and hold circuit can achieve the total harmonic distortion (THD) of 66dB and noise of 62 dB with power consumption of 1.6mW at 1-V supply voltage. The sample and hold circuit can achieve 10-bit resolution ay 1-V supply voltage in nanometer CMOS Technology.

Keywords: Operational amplifier, sample and hold circuit, switched-capacitor, open-loop DC gain, THD.

Design & Implementation of 5-Stage 32-bit RISC-V Pipeline Processor on FPGA

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ABSTRACT

The proposed work focuses on designing and implementing a Harvard Architecture-based 32-bit RISC-V processor, using the open instruction set to enhance speed and performance. The processor leverages pipelining, comprising five stages—instruction fetch, decode, execute, memory access, and write back—and operates within a single cycle to improve CPI (clock cycles per instruction). The control unit plays a crucial role in managing the smooth execution of each pipeline stage operation. A hazard detection unit is designed to address potential pipeline hazards, which utilizes registers to handle pipeline hazards like data dependency and prevent stalls. Branch instructions, which can introduce delays and reduce efficiency, are addressed through the Static Branch Predictor. The branch predictor reduces CPI by saving one clock cycle during branch execution, which enhances the processor's overall performance. All components of the processor are designed in Verilog and simulated in Vivado. For hardware implementation, this code is synthesized into a gate-level netlist, which optimizes the design for FPGA architecture. Implementation follows, where the netlist is mapped to FPGA resources and then routed to a specific location on board. This processor design is tested using the Xilinx Vivado toolchain to verify its functionality and efficiency. Finally, the bitstream is generated and loaded onto the ZedBoard Zynq Evaluation and Development Kit (xc7z020clg484-1) FPGA for real-time testing and evaluation. To visually demonstrate the instruction execution process, two 7-segment displays are connected via Pmod headers on the FPGA board. These displays offer real-time feedback on the instruction sequence being executed, which allows for easy observation and verification of the processor's operational stages. Keywords: RISC-V Processor, Pipeline, Static Branch Predictor, Xilinx Vivado, FPGA.

A Comprehensive Study of the Ionospheric Response to Two Intense 2 Geomagnetic Storms of Solar Cycle 24 over Asian and American 3 Region: A Comparative Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Geomagnetic storms are space weather events that greatly impact the earth's magnetosphere and ionosphere, causing disturbances in satellite communication, navigation systems, and ground-based power grids. This study investigates the ionospheric irregularities in response to two intense geomagnetic storms (march 2015 and June 2015) of solar cycle 24 over two longitudinal sectors. In order to analyze the ionospheric response, sound analysis of solar wind parameters (of the above-mentioned events) and total electron content (TEC) variations (via line as well as contour plots) is presented. The results show significant seasonal diurnal as well as regional TEC variations, indicating distinct response to solar wind parameters, specifically the interplanetary magnetic field B_z component, which are highly correlated with the storm's intensity. During both events significant TEC enhancement can be seen during the early hours of the storms, which vary longitudinally. The findings of this study can be used to improve space weather modeling and prediction, ultimately helping mitigate the adverse effects of space weather on technological systems.

Keywords: Geomagnetic storm, Ionospheric irregularities, Solar activity, Ionospheric VTEC variation, St Patrik day storm

Removal of Dyes from Aqueous Medium using Metal doped Hydroxyapatite: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Presence of dyes in wastewater is a major problem due to its detrimental effects on the environment and human health. A variety of organic contaminants, including dyes, medicines, pesticides, drugs, and pharmaceutical waste, have escaped into water sources, causes severe water adulteration. Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a biocompatible adsorbent that is effective in removing both cationic and anionic dyes among the different adsorbents that are used. HAp can have a hexagonal or monoclinic structure. Doping hydroxyapatite with other metals improved remarkably its removal efficiency which gain a lot of attention recently. A variety of methods, including hydrothermal, chemical precipitation, sol-gel, and mechanochemical, were used to synthesized Metal HAp nano composites. The synthesized material of HAp was characterized using X-ray Diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. HAp doped with copper metal ion (Cu) was found to be enhanced the adsorption capacity of HAp against Congo red dye. Copper doping significantly increased the dye degradation, 99% dye was degraded upon 0.63% Cu doping, whereas 75% dye degradation occurred in pure HAp. HAp doped with Palladium (Pd) ions was efficient in removal of Methylene blue (MB) dye. After 120 min of irradiation, the removal efficiency for the highest Pd contribution was approximately 86.4%. The recent advances in the use of metal doped HAp nano composites for the removal of toxic dyes will be beneficial to mitigate the detrimental effect of the toxic dyes on the environment and human health. The continued advancement and application of metal-doped hydroxyapatite hold great promise for improving water quality and addressing the global challenge of dye pollution.

Keywords: Metal Doped Hydroxyapatite, Dyes, Biocompatible adsorbent, Removal efficiency.

Analysis of Medical Physics at Radiological Medical Facilities in Sindh

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ABSTRACT

Sindh is the second largest province of Pakistan in terms of population. The healthcare sector of the province has acquired hi-tech modalities for cancer diagnosis and treatment. This rapid development has opened new doors for medical physicists while creating additional challenges in a country like Pakistan where education and training structure for medical physicists is not at par with developed countries. The availability of medical physicists at the radiological medical facilities (like radiotherapy and nuclear medicine) is a mandatory requirement of the Pakistan Nuclear Regulatory Authority (PNRA) and of paramount importance for patient protection. Material and Methods: The educational and training related aspects of medical physics profession have been discussed in this paper, particularly for Sindh province. Currently, no university is offering dedicated degree program in medical physics in the province. The NED University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi has started MS Physics with specialization in medical physics. Furthermore, a certification process does not exist anywhere in the province or country. Whereas, hi-tech modalities like cyclotrons, gammaknife, cyberknife, MR-LINAC, IORT, tomotherapy, etc. are now available in Sindh province. Currently, seven cyclotrons, three gammaknife, two cyberknife, two MR-LINAC and other facilities are available in the province, which makes it clearly ahead from rest of the country in terms of availability of cancer diagnosis and treatment facilities. The IAEA database for cyclotrons indicates that Karachi is at par with the cities like New York, Sydney, etc. in terms of number of medical cyclotrons. Despite the absence of a dedicated degree program in medical physics, the

medical physics community has responded to this situation in exceptional manner and many medical physicists have either acquired international medical physics certification or opted a PhD degree in radiation or medical physics. Coupled with this, the regular trainings, workshops and conferences have increased the knowledge and awareness about the profession among the students. The activities of medical physicists, through various groups and platform, have created a positive learning culture. Similarly, the spending of the healthcare sector and expansion in facilities has triggered a wave of opportunities for the young medical physicists in Sindh province. Results and Conclusion: The medical physics profession is of prime importance for radiotherapy and nuclear medicine facilities. With the advancement of technology, the training and re-training of medical physicists has become an essential item to ensure quality and safety. In Sindh province, the adequate level of competence is being maintained through the implementation of PNRA requirements of education and training of medical physicists and through continuous ongoing workshops, trainings, international certifications and conferences.

Ideally, a dedicated medical physics degree program and a certification system should be established in the province. This will make the structure of medical physics profession in accordance with the IAEA safety standards.

Keywords: Medical Physics, Medical Facilities at Sindh, Hi-tech Modalities

Dielectric Relaxation & Hopping Mechanisms of Charge Transport In $La_{0.3}Ca_{0.7}MnO_3$

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ABSTRACT

In this research work the structural, electrical magnetic and basic properties of $La_{0.3}Ca_{0.7}MnO_3$ has been explored through XRD, Impedance Spectroscopy and magnetic investigation. Polycrystalline sample of $La_{0.3}Ca_{0.7}MnO_3$ is set up by conventional solid state reaction route. A newly synthesized $La_{0.3}Ca_{0.7}MnO_3$ sample is examined for the basic properties through high resolution XRD technique for the recognizable proof of a polycrystalline sample phases that affirm its phase purity, space group, bond length, bond angles, different lattice parameter. Other structural data of their unit cell at atomic level is explored with the help of Fullprof program. The interaction of various electrical parameters under the variety of temperature and frequency are studied utilizing impedance spectroscopy. This is helpful and surely understood procedure is chosen and utilized as a device to examine the conduction mechanism, dielectric constant, different relaxation processes, electrical conductivity and activation energies associated with conduction of charge carriers. The Apparatus Alpha-N high resolution dielectric analyzer is utilized for the estimating of impedance in this work. We utilized WINDETA programming (which is completely mechanized) for enlisting the information to get helpful electrical data of the sample at different temperature and frequency. ZView software is utilized for getting the electrical information with the assistance of equivalent circuit model. Hopping Conduction model are utilized to test the conduction behavior, localization length and activation energies of charge carrier.

Investigation of Charge Transport Through Grains & Grain Boundaries of $\text{Sm}_{0.2}\text{Ca}_{0.8}\text{MnO}_3$ Using Impedance Spectroscopy

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ABSTRACT

The SmMnO_3 compound was synthesized using the solid-state reaction technique, with various compositions prepared by doping calcium at different concentrations on the A-site ($\text{Sm}_{1-x}\text{Ca}_x\text{MnO}_3$). A concise overview of the experimental techniques employed to analyze the structural and electrical properties is provided. The structural, magnetic, and electrical characteristics of the synthesized samples were investigated using synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD) and impedance spectroscopy. Impedance spectroscopy was utilized to assess the electrical parameters of the material across a range of temperatures. Several conduction models were applied to elucidate the transport mechanisms in different phases of the sample as a function of frequency. The electrical properties of grain boundaries, calculated from experimental data using a circuit model, revealed variations in electrical transport phenomena between 78K and 108K. The study examined the activation energies of charge carriers and relaxation frequencies associated with the imaginary components of various electrical parameters, considering the substantial hopping induced by the double exchange mechanism between Mn^{3+} and Mn^{4+} ions. To further explore conduction behavior, activation energy, and localization energy, impedance data were fitted using AZ view software, achieving a 2-3 percent fitting error through an analogous circuit model. Conduction models such as Arrhenius and variable-range hopping (VRH) were employed to analyze these properties.

Keywords: Manganite's; Conduction Mechanism; Small Polaron Hopping; Variable Range Hopping

Structural and Morphological Properties of Laser Irradiated Bio materials

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ABSTRACT

On heating di-calcium phosphate dehydrate $\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to 750°C , the β - $\text{Ca}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ is obtained. The materials were then pressed at 4 tons for 5 minutes for preparation of pallets. The pallets were then dried at 120°C in a vacuum Chamber for 4 hours. The materials were sintered in a muffle furnace at 450°C for 24 hours, this resulted to grey color γ - $\text{Ca}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ phase. Further sintering at 750°C for 24 hours resulted in tetragonal beta $\text{Ca}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ phase with lattice constants to obtain $a=b=6.684\text{\AA}$ and $c=24.144\text{\AA}$. The pallets were prepared from Di-Calcium Phosphate Di-Hydrate triclinic $2\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ powder was used to obtain three different phases Gamma, Beta, Alpha. These three different phases were obtained at 450°C , 750°C and 1050°C respectively.

The pallets having mean thickness of 0.12 cm were characterized by monochromated x-Ray Diffraction technique, high resolution optical microscopy. Before sintering micro-cracks were frequently seen on the palleted surfaces but then cracks disappeared after sintering at 750°C . Grey colored gamma phase was found to be harder than the white colored Beta Phase. SEM were also recorded for 450°C and 750°C pallets sintered for different periods and laser irradiation with Nd: YAG laser with some special specifications.

Keywords: sintering, calcium phosphoate, CaHPO_4

Semi-relativistic effect on non-linear electron acoustic wave

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ABSTRACT

Nonlinear electron acoustic waves are investigated theoretically and numerically using the fundamental fluid quantum hydrodynamics (QHD) in the semi relativistic plasmas. Semi-relativistic effects give contribution as in kinematic effects and in interparticle interaction We consider a spin up and spin down electron as a two distinct fluid. In plasma electron as a two distinct fluid are regarded as degenerate. We neglect the effect of external magnetic field. A QHD model that includes the quantum force associated with Bohm potential Fermi Dirac pressure law. A Korteweg-de-Vries equation driving the dynamics of EAWs is developed by using the conventional reductive perturbation technique in conjunction with the quantum hydrodynamic model. It is shown that the electron acoustic soliton exists for immobile ions, single spin semi-relativistic plasmas. The parameters of the spin electron acoustic soliton are examined in relation to concentration, exchange interaction, and Darwin term. Darwin term impact on the non-linear system's dispersion characteristics. The spinless semi-relativistic effects, in the form of the Darwin term, have a major impact on both spinless and spinning particle plasmas. The existence of spin acoustic soliton is analyzed with density variation of spin up and down electrons. The effect is observed on the width and amplitude of soliton. The amplitude of the wave is independent of the quantum parameter H .

Keywords: Quantum hydrodynamic model, Electron acoustic waves

Investigation of Prevalence, Risk Factors, and Associated Contributors of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus Among Pregnant Women of Local Population

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is a common metabolic condition during pregnancy, causing hyperglycemia in pregnant women. GDM usually occurs in the middle of the pregnancy period, between 24 and 28 weeks of gestation. The etiology of diabetes is multifactorial and not fully defined, but in most cases, hyperglycemia is the result of impaired glucose tolerance due to dysfunction of pancreatic B cells or defects in the insulin signaling cascade. GDM is typically diagnosed using blood glucose levels from an oral glucose tolerance test.

Objectives: To analyze data of diagnosed GDM patients from Hassan Abdal and surrounding hospitals.

Methodology: The study at Hospitals in Tehsil Hassan Abdal District Attock involved 202 primigravida mothers, 104 with GDM and 98 Normal. GDM was diagnosed using the 75g Oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT). The history of the subjects including age, locality (Rural/Urban), maternal demographic (ethnicity) and psychological risk factors, etc. are recorded in the proforma especially developed for this purpose. The study has been approved by Research Ethical Committees of UW, Wah Cantt. All mothers were advised on diet, exercise, and self-monitored capillary blood glucose levels.

Conclusion: To sum up, this study measures the effect of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) on negative outcomes for mothers and newborns. The results emphasize the highest prevalence of GDM was found within age group 30-32. Majority of the GDM belong to Rural area and they were Punjabi (40.38%). The psychology of mothers is measured by using perceived stress scale (PSS). The PSS score is high. This information is essential for policymakers and healthcare providers, helping to create improved diabetes prevention and management approaches worldwide.

Unlocking Nature's Arsenal: Drug design with *Zanthoxylum armatum* against Malaria

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ABSTRACT

Malaria remains a significant global health challenge, necessitating innovative approaches in drug development to address the growing resistance of the Plasmodium parasite. In this study, we explored the potential of the herb *Zanthoxylum armatum* as a treatment for malaria, given its rich composition of phytochemicals. Using molecular docking techniques, we focused on the interactions between these phytochemicals and key malarial receptor proteins: PfAMA1, IF9-3D7, PvRON2, and PfAMA1. Among the various compounds analyzed, α -Amyrins exhibited the strongest docking efficiency, suggesting its potential as a promising anti-malarial candidate. PfAMA1 and PvRON2 are crucial receptor proteins involved in the invasion mechanisms of *Plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium falciparum*, making them attractive targets for drug development. The successful binding of α -Amyrins to these proteins highlights its potential to disrupt the parasite's invasion process. Gaining insight into the molecular interactions between α -Amyrins and malarial proteins could provide the structural foundation for designing new anti-malarial therapies. These findings contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of natural products in combating malaria. With its diverse array of bioactive compounds, *Zanthoxylum armatum* serves as a valuable resource for drug discovery. However, further experimental studies are required to validate the efficacy, safety, and potential of α -Amyrins and its derivatives as a novel class of anti-malarial agents. This research marks an important step in leveraging nature's resources for the development of effective and sustainable anti-malarial treatments.

Keywords: Malaria, Drug development, *Zanthoxylum armatum*, Phytoconstituents, Molecular docking

ODACTRA HOUSE DUST MITE ALLERGEN TABLET FOR SUBLINGUAL USE – SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND:

ODACTRA is a prescription medicine used for sublingual (under the tongue) immunotherapy to treat house dust mite allergies that can cause sneezing, runny or itchy nose, stuffy or congested nose, or itchy and watery eyes. ODACTRA may be prescribed for persons 12 through 65 years of age who are allergic to house dust mites. ODACTRA is NOT a medication that gives immediate relief for symptoms of house dust mite allergy and some adverse effects are also reported by using ODACTRA sublingually.

OBJECTIVE:

The purpose of this systematic review is to assess the efficacy of sublingual ODACTRA in managing specific health issues, gather reported patient experiences in previous years including any adverse events and to provide any other alternative dosage form to improve patient compliance and subside adverse events if found any.

METHODOLOGY:

To write a systematic review, PubMed database search was utilized and keywords and truncation techniques were used by using the search terms allergy, allergic rhinitis, asthma, allergic asthma, house dust mite, allergen immunotherapy, subcutaneous immunotherapy, sublingual immunotherapy, transdermal, MK-8237 for the collection of relevant data published between 2014–2024. 54 articles were downloaded on topic under observation. A total of 43 articles were selected after abstracting relevant information from the studies and assessing quality, data synthesized and presented by following PRISMA.

RESULT:

According to this research and reported data ODACTRA should be administered through sub cutaneous or transdermal route in those patients who cannot be treated by ODACTRA sublingually. As per research SCIT gives more efficacy than SLIT in asthma and allergic rhinitis.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the subcutaneous administration of ODACTRA has shown greater efficacy compared to the sublingual ODACTRA tablet in individuals aged 18 to 65 years and older. This superiority in efficacy may be attributed to more consistent and controlled delivery of the allergen, leading to better immunological outcomes and symptom control in this age group. On the other hand, for individuals below 18 years and adolescents, transdermal administration of ODACTRA emerges as a preferable option. This method offers a non-invasive and patient-friendly approach, which is particularly advantageous for younger populations who may have difficulties with sublingual or subcutaneous routes. The transdermal system ensures steady absorption and reduces the risk of adverse reactions, making it a safe and effective choice for managing allergies in younger patients. Overall, tailoring the route of ODACTRA administration based on age and patient preferences can optimize treatment outcomes and improve adherence to allergy immunotherapy.

KEYWORD:

HDM, SLIT, SCIT, ALLERGIC RHINITIS, ASTHMA MONOSENSITIZED

EXPLORING THE NEURODEVELOPMENTAL TRAJECTORIES AND THERAPEUTIC APPROACHES IN AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER (ASD)

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION:

This research work delves into the intricate realm of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), a sophisticated neurodevelopmental condition characterized by persistent challenges in social communication and interaction, along with distinct patterns of restricted and repetitive behaviors.

OBJECTIVES:

Through an in-depth exploration of neurodevelopmental trajectories and therapeutic methodologies, the study analyzes recent scientific findings and diverse research approaches. The understanding of these pathways is deemed critical for developing targeted interventions and personalized treatments, ultimately enhancing the quality of life for individuals on the autism spectrum.

METHODOLOGY:

This is a review-based observational descriptive study focusing on the last 20-years. The sampling technique involves a systematic search and retrieval of articles from major academic databases, which include Google scholar, Cochrane library, PubMed, NIH and science direct engines. The study encompasses a global perspective, utilizing the data from diverse geographical locations.

CONCLUSION:

The conclusion emphasizes implications and highlights the roles of genetic and environmental factors, as well as abnormalities in brain connectivity and neural circuitry in ASD development.

RESULT:

The study's findings highlight the ASD's genetic complexities, emphasizing advances in genomics and identifying potential risk genes. It underscores applied behavior analysis (ABA) as the preferred intervention, providing a comprehensive review of ABA approaches and their demonstrated efficacy in improving communication, social skills, and behavior management in children with ASD.

KEYWORDS: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Neurodevelopmental trajectories, ABA approaches

From Floral to Calm: Evaluating the Anxiolytic Activity of Aqueous Infusion of Jasmine Flower

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence of anxiety disorders among students is alarmingly high, manifesting symptoms such as restlessness, dizziness, fatigue, muscle tension, and chest pain. Anxiety disorders pose a significant burden on mental health, with limited treatment options and considerable side effects, impacting quality of life and posing a socio-economic burden. Natural products offer a safer and more cost-effective alternate to treat numerous conditions. Among different natural options, *Jasminum officinale*, commonly known as jasmine belongs to family Oleaceae is an aromatic herb traditionally used to alleviate anxiety disorders. However, the pharmacological basis for its medicinal use in anxiety remains unexplored. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of jasmine extract in anxiety disorders. We investigated the anxiolytic effect of jasmine extract infusion in BALB/c mice using Elevated Plus Maze and Light and dark assay. The infusion was prepared by boiling jasmine flowers in water, followed by cooling and filtration. Different doses (50ml/kg, 100ml/kg, and 150ml/kg) were administered to mice, with normal saline serving as a control. The results showed a dose-dependent increase in anxiolytic effect, attributed to the presence of GABA (gamma-aminobutyric acid). Our findings suggest that jasmine flower extract exhibits a promising anxiolytic effect, warranting further research to explore its potential as a natural remedy for anxiety disorders.

INNOVATIVE SHAMPOO FORMULATION WITH SULFATE & PARABENS REPLACEMENT TO CONTROL HAIR PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

Cleaning with shampoo is a fairly popular hair care procedure. It is true that hair will remain shiny for a very long time if individuals take care of it by routinely washing and conditioning the scalp and hair roots. Sebaceous glands secrete sebum, an oil that keeps hair hydrated, and this oil is what the hair gets. Hair that has been moisturized is less prone to break or appear frizzy and dry. Different types of Shampoo are primarily a product use to clean hair and scalp to remove dirt. Nowadays in market it is observed that many herbal and natural products working better than synthetic because of some harmful chemical reactions and side effects of synthetic shampoos. So, from these literatures we have identified that people are considering herbal/natural as their first choice as compared to synthetic ones, herbal/ natural Shampoo works better and is safer than synthetic varieties. It is difficult to change thinking of people rather than to change harmful ingredients with beneficial ingredients which also provide satisfaction to consumers by making foam. In this formulation Sulfate has been replaced with decyl glucoside which is less harmful and also a good foaming agent. This nonionic surfactant has been extensively utilized for many years in rinse-off products like shampoos, hair colorants, and soaps because of its strong foaming ability and excellent tolerance. This one is less toxic and more affordable than other synthetic products. Decyl glucoside removes dirt and oils from formulations by reducing the surface tension between two liquids thanks to its functions as a surfactant. Recent research suggests that decyl glucoside and sulfate-based shampoos differ significantly in terms of their gentleness and cleansing efficacy. Shampoos containing sulfates, such as sodium lauryl sulfate (SLES) and sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS), are well-known for their potent cleansing abilities, removing oil and dirt from hair with ease. However, these sulfates are also linked to potential disadvantages, such as stripping natural oils from the hair and scalp, which can cause dryness and irritation, especially in people with sensitive skin (Author, Year). Decyl glucoside shampoos, on the other hand, use

gentler surfactants from natural sources like glucose and fatty alcohols. Decyl glucoside-based formulations, according to studies, maintain adequate foaming and emulsifying properties while exhibiting gentler cleansing actions (Author, Year). As a result, consumers who are looking for sulfate-free alternatives that are less likely to irritate the scalp or upset the hair's natural moisture balance are increasingly turning to them. Decyl glucoside shampoos are a reflection of a growing preference for gentler, eco-friendlier personal care products that still provide effective cleansing.

AutoMed: Revolutionizing Way of Giving Medicine for Chronic Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Introduction:

The management of chronic conditions poses significant challenges for patients, caregivers, and healthcare professionals alike. Traditional methods of medication administration often rely on patient adherence, which can be inconsistent and may lead to suboptimal outcomes. In response to these challenges, AutoMed emerges as a revolutionary solution, integrating continuous monitoring and automated drug delivery for enhanced patient care.

Methodology:

AutoMed operates through a wearable device affixed to the biceps region, seamlessly integrating into the wearer's daily routine. Equipped with advanced sensors, it continuously monitors vital parameters and biomarkers associated with the specific chronic condition. Through real-time data analysis, AutoMed detects fluctuations in these parameters, signaling the need for medication intervention.

Results:

Preliminary studies demonstrate the efficacy and feasibility of AutoMed in improving medication adherence and health outcomes for individuals with chronic conditions. By providing timely and precise drug delivery based on personalized physiological data, AutoMed offers a paradigm shift in the management of chronic illnesses. Furthermore, its user-friendly design promotes patient autonomy and empowerment, fostering a collaborative approach to healthcare.

SECRET TO SOFT PROTECTED LIPS: UNLOCKING THE BENEFITS OF SPF LIP BALM.

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ABSTRACT

These days, everyone is focused on skin care and cosmetics. This Lipluxe product provides a 3-in-1 solution for lip care, offering broad-spectrum sun protection, moisturizing nourishment, and a subtle, natural-looking tint. Its unique formula combines physical and chemical, emollient-rich moisturizers, and antioxidant Phyto-extracts to shield, hydrate, and perfect lips.

Lip care is an essential aspect of the daily skincare routine, as the lips are particularly susceptible to environmental stressors. To address these concerns, a new generation of lip balms has emerged, combining protective, nourishing, and cosmetic benefits. The preparation of SPF tinted lip balm involves a meticulous multi-step process to ensure high-quality results. Active ingredients and colorants are precisely measured, and various components such as beeswax, almond oil, shea butter, humectants, preservatives, and natural UV ingredients like green tea extract are carefully combined through controlled mixing and blending for uniform distribution. The texture, consistency, and color are optimized through incremental adjustments, and moisturizing ingredients are added to enhance lip hydration.

We performed different tests on our product, such as smoothness, spreadability, pH test, shelf life, etc., and the results showed that its texture, comfortable wear, and convenient packaging make it an ideal choice for daily use. By addressing the complex needs of lip care, this SPF tinted lip balm provides comprehensive solution for protecting, nourishing, and perfecting the lips.

Keywords: Hydrating, SPF, Lip balm

Comparative Evaluation of Temocillin and Ceftolozane Against E. coli and S. aureus: Sensitivity and Resistance Patterns

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ABSTRACT

Main objective of the study was to evaluate recent sensitivity pattern of Staphylococcus aureus and E. coli. Total of eighty specimens of Staphylococcus aureus and E. coli were collected from different laboratories of Karachi and results were analyzed at Faculty of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutics, Hamdard University Karachi. The antibiotics tested for sensitivity were temocillin and Ceftolozane. The antibiotic susceptibility test of the bacterial isolates was performed by Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method [1]. Out of seventy samples 68% samples showed sensitivity against temocillin, 12.85% showed an intermediate behavior and 18.57% showed resistant towards the temocillin. Ceftolozane had sensitivity pattern 31.42% resistant 14%, intermediate and 48.57% sensitivity against S. aureus. Numerous studies have demonstrated high sensitivity rates ($\geq 90\%$) for temocillin's overall effectiveness against E. coli. It works especially well against strains of Escherichia coli that produce extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs). Temocillin exhibits 20% to 60% sensitivity rates and moderate to low efficacy against S. aureus. In strains of S. aureus that are resistant to methicillin (MRSA), it is less effective.

Keywords: MRSA, E. coli, S. aureus, ESBL, Temocillin

CALCIUM BASED ANTACID TO NEUTRALIZE STOMACH ACIDITY, QUICK RELIEF FOR LONG PERIOD OF TIME.

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ABSTRACT

This calcium-based antacids can provide quick relief; they may not be suitable for long-term use or for individuals with certain medical conditions. Always consult with a health care profession for proper advice. Our aim about its study is that to evaluate therapeutic effects and safety profile of calcium-based antacids in neutralizing stomach acid, relief heartburn and its stability and suitability for long period of time or in individual with specific medical conditions. The methodology involves reviewing the chemical properties and mechanisms of action of ingredients of calcium-based antacid, also assess their effectiveness and safety by analyzing the formulation of product and patient outcomes. Calcium-based antacids neutralize stomach acid by reacting with hydrochloric acid (HCl) to form calcium chloride, water, and carbon dioxide, increasing the stomach's pH and reducing acidity. This reaction also buffers the stomach's pH, maintaining it within a narrow range, and creates an environment less favorable for acid-loving bacteria. This calcium-based antacids can form a protective barrier on the esophagus, shielding it from acid reflux, and slow down gastric motility, reducing the acid reflux. This mechanism provides effective relief from heartburn and prevents stomach acidity. It indicate that that our product (calcium based antacid) effectively neutralize stomach acid , and quick relief from indigestion and heartburn. Its study also emphasizes that its long-term use led to potential adverse effects like hypercalcemia, also point that is not recommended for individuals with certain health conditions without medical guidance and

complete review of patient profile. The importance to understand both benefits and limitations of product (calcium based antacid) . This also helps for rapid symptoms relief, its prolonged use could lead to adverse events and complications such as kidney stone, hypercalcemia, also altered calcium metabolism. It's also urged that combining calcium with other ingredients like magnesium it's may reduce side effects and improve therapeutic effect but individual outcomes and health conditions must be considered. This product is suggested to explore more effective formulation and safer to establish with clear recommendations for use in different patients

KEY WORDS: reduce intense heart burn by calcium-long term effect – peptic ulcer treatment.

Empowering Pink Minds: Unveiling Breast Health Awareness Among Pakistani University Students

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ABSTRACT

The increasing incidence of breast cancer is a global concern, and early detection is crucial for patient outcomes and disease prevention. A study evaluating breast cancer awareness among Pakistani university students in Karachi identified cultural beliefs, social stigma, and a lack of easily accessible information as key factors hindering effective breast health education. The primary objective is to evaluate breast cancer awareness levels among Pakistani university students, delving into the underlying factors contributing to limited insights. The research was carried out in Karachi, involving the participation of four hundred and thirty female students who completed a well-structured online questionnaire and the data was analyzed by using IBM SPSS Statistics. The study assessed awareness levels, frequency of routine Breast Self-Examinations, factors influencing knowledge and participation in awareness efforts, and the correlation between respondents' likelihood of regular exercise and breast cancer prevention. The study found an 89% awareness of "breast cancer" among respondents, yet revealed a concern with a low percentage practicing routine Breast Self-Examinations (BSE). This underscores the necessity for targeted educational initiatives to emphasize early diagnosis. A discrepancy exists between knowledge and active involvement in breast cancer awareness, with a low likelihood of regular exercise indicating an opportunity for interventions emphasizing lifestyle choices in preventing breast cancer. The ultimate goal is to improve early identification, prevention, and overall outcomes by fostering a proactive and knowledgeable culture around breast health in Pakistan.

Keywords: Breast cancer, awareness, early detection, prevention

Knee Osteoarthritis Among Adults in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most widespread musculoskeletal condition, primarily affecting weight-bearing joints like the knees and hips. Both intrinsic and extrinsic risk factors contribute to its development. According to WHO About 73% of people with OA are older than 55 years, and 60% are female. most frequently affected joint. This research based investigate the prevalence, risk factors, and demographic patterns of osteoarthritis. Questionnaire-based survey and evaluate some important parameters by respondent with the help of SPSS software. This cross-sectional descriptive study, conducted in 2023, surveyed a population. The questionnaire included 33 questions on functional activities, painful activities, and joint stiffness and swelling. data analyzed by the SPSS software version 20.0. According to the data, 76.2% of the participants were females and 23.8% were male, the prevalence of age was about 91% range from 18-37 years old while 9% were range from above 37 up to 57 years old. 37.8% have a family history of osteoarthritis, 43.3% do not, and 18.9% not aware.12.4% people are facing difficulty in walking, running etc. and 30% facing the swelling around the joints and bending the knee.11.7% of participants have been diagnosed with osteoarthritis in one or both knees, while 88.3% have never been told they have the condition. Our survey on knee osteoarthritis awareness showed that most of the population has a basic understanding, 11.7% are affected. Efforts are needed to raise awareness, reduce the risk of disabilities, and promote early diagnosis.

Keywords: osteoarthritis, awareness, Population Survey

CUSTOMIZING CARE: THE ERA OF PERSONALIZED PHARMACOGENOMICS

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ABSTRACT

This section introduces the dynamic and evolving field of pharmacogenomics, which is the study of how genes affect a person's response to drugs. Emphasizing its transformative impact on personalized medicine. Also highlighting the key role of the Personalized Medicine Coalition (PMC) in advancing targeted therapies within precision medicine. To delving into the potential and implications of pharmacogenomics for personalized medicine. To explore how genetic profiling can aid clinicians in identifying effective approaches to preventing, diagnosing, treating, and managing various diseases. To emphasize the role of genetic testing and the identification of genetic variations associated with treatment responses. This is a review-based observational descriptive study focusing on the last 20 years. The sampling technique involves a systematic search and retrieval of articles from major academic databases, which include Google Scholar, Cochrane Library, PubMed, NIH, and Science Direct engines. The study encompasses a global perspective, utilizing the data from diverse geographical locations. The results highlight the potential of personalized medicine in revolutionizing treatment approaches for specific diseases. The focus is on cancer, cardiovascular diseases, neurological disorders, infectious diseases, and autoimmune disorders. The study concludes by summarizing key insights and highlighting the transformative impact of pharmacogenomics on future healthcare landscapes. The challenges identified, including genetic variability, data interpretation, cost and accessibility, and ethical considerations, are acknowledged. The conclusion emphasizes the need for collaborative efforts, advancements in technology, clarification of legal and ethical concerns, healthcare professional education, and public awareness to further the field of personalized medicine.

Keywords: Pharmacogenomics, Personalized medicine, Genetic profiling, Targeted therapies, Genetic variations

NANO-TECHNOLOGY IN PHARMACEUTICAL INNOVATIONS FOR ADVANCED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Nanotechnology is about employing materials and devices at a tiny scale, involving their design, creation, analysis, and use. In pharmaceutical sciences, these specialized materials and devices are innovated to interact accurately with cells and tissues at a level of molecules.

Objective(s): Comprehensively collect and assess a wide array of published literature, studies, and research papers concerning the utilization of nanotechnology in advanced drug delivery systems within pharmaceutical sciences. Explore enhancement of drug solubility, absorption rates, and bioavailability through nanotechnology-based formulations. Assess prevailing challenges and issues linked to nanomaterials, with a focus on identifying specific areas requiring additional research and development efforts.

Methodology: The methodology involves a systematic review and meta-analysis of existing literature focusing on the application of nanotechnology in advanced drug delivery systems. The study will be conducted utilizing online databases, scholarly repositories, and scientific journals. Primary tools for this study will include sophisticated literature search engines (e.g., PubMed), academic databases, and inclusion/exclusion criteria to identify.

Results: The results aim to inform that these tools significantly improve drug targeting, enhance pharmacokinetics and bioavailability, improve the effectiveness of treatments by precisely delivering therapeutics to specific biological targets.

Conclusion: This technology offers a promising avenue for managing toxicity in certain conditions, where drug toxicity from chemotherapy is a primary concern. Despite their significance, the potential toxicity of various nanoparticles utilized in drug delivery systems remains a substantial concern. Hence, it's vital to identify and evaluate the toxic traits of these nanomaterials.

Keywords: Nanoscale Materials, Targeted Therapy, Minimized Toxicity, Therapeutic Efficacy.

Eco-Friendly Foundation for Lasting Impact

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ABSTRACT

These days, everyone is focused on skin care and cosmetics. It doesn't matter what gender you are; foundation is necessary to set your skin and cover any imperfections. A makeup foundation is an essential component of makeup and gives flawless skin to a person's face. Any makeup process must start with foundation since it serves as the base upon which the rest of the look is constructed. In the context of cosmetics, it has two functions: it evens out skin tone and texture and acts as a foundation for additional makeup application. At its core, foundation aims to create a uniform complexion by concealing imperfections such as blemishes, redness, and discoloration. By providing coverage, it lays the groundwork for a polished appearance, allowing other makeup products to adhere better and last longer. Additionally, foundation can help to mattify or hydrate the skin, depending on the formulation, addressing various skin concerns and preferences. This article on foundation will give you diverse knowledge about its benefits, and potential impact on skin health. A makeup foundation sets the foundation for the face before any application of another makeup product. Our foundation has the ability to combine three things into one, i.e., it plays the roles of foundation, sunscreen, and sunblock at the same time. This means that it not only sets your makeup but also protects your skin from sunburn, tanning, and patches which allows you to stay in the sun for almost 10 hours as it will fight against the UV rays of the sun. We have performed different tests on our product such as Smoothness, Spread ability, pH test, Patch test, Visible or invisible microbial growth, Shelf life etc. and We also used this product on test subjects after we were sure that it won't have any side effects on skin.

Keywords: foundation, SPF, hydrate, cosmetics

Assessment of Carabeef and Beef for The Production of Quality Nuggets

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ABSTRACT

Red meat has a better nutrient profile than white meat due to more iron. Nuggets are a popular snack, ready-to-cook meal and are enjoyed worldwide. The nugget's quality can be greatly impacted by processing techniques and ingredients. Beef and carabeef along various flour source may variate in product. Scanty information drive to plan and find out the effect of the source of meat (Cara beef and beef) and source of flour (wheat and corn) on the quality of nuggets. The Longissimus dorsi muscle meat was used to make the nuggets. The chemical composition, emulsion stability, cooking yield, cooking loss, and water-holding capacity of the nuggets were all examined in this investigation. Significant variations in the qualitative attributes of the nuggets according to the type of meat and wheat used were shown by the results of the numerous tests and analyses. Beef shows greater water holding capacity (30.988%) compared to Cara beef (25.138%), with a significant difference ($P < 0.001$) whereas Carabeef is more tender (6.567 kg/cm²) and shows higher chromaticity (18.877) as compared to beef tenderness (5.983 kg/cm²) and chromaticity (16.227) with a significant difference ($P < 0.001$). The best quality nugget was made using Cara beef flesh and wheat flour in terms of general acceptability, nutritional value, and sensory aspects.

Keywords: Beef, Carabeef, Nugget production, Nugget quality, Wheat flour

Synthesis, Structure Elucidation and Biological Screening of N-(4-((6-methoxy-8-quinoline-yl) amine) pentyl) benzene sulfonamide Derivatives

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ABSTRACT

A new series of N-substituted derivatives of primaquine sulfonamide N-(4-((6-methoxy-8-quinoline-yl) amine) pentyl) benzene sulfonamide (3S) has been synthesized. Antibacterial activity of these compounds was screened out against different bacterial strains. N-(4-((6-methoxyquinolin-8-yl) pentane-1,4diamine (1S) was used as precursor to synthesize N-alkyl/aralkyl-N-(4-((6-methoxy-8-quinoline-yl) amine) pentyl) benzene sulfonamide derivatives 3S-a to 3S-f. Compound (1S) was reacted with aryl sulfonyl chloride (2S) in the presence of 10% aqueous solution of Na₂CO₃ to synthesize N-(4-((6-methoxy-8-quinoline-yl) amine) pentyl) benzene sulfonamide (3S). The molecule 3S was further treated with alkyl/aralkyl halides (4). The structure of synthesized molecules was confirmed by using IR, ¹H-NMR, and EIMS spectroscopy. The antibacterial % age inhabitation these compounds proved them strong to moderate inhibitors relative to standard Ciprofloxacin.

Keywords: N-(4-((6-methoxyquinolin-8-yl) pentane-1, 4 diamine, antibacterial activity, aryl sulfonylchloride

Development of PANI/g-C₃N₄ Nanocomposite for Enhanced Super Capacitor Performance

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ABSTRACT

Polyaniline (PANI) have attracted considerable attention across a wide spectrum of scientific and technological fields due to its straightforward synthesis, conductivity, cost-effectiveness, optical versatility and electrochemical properties. In this study, we have synthesized PANI, graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄), and PANI/g-C₃N₄ composites through chemical oxidative polymerization, thermal degradation and in-situ polymerization techniques respectively. XRD, FTIR, SEM and UV-visible spectroscopic techniques were employed to scrutinize the structural, morphological and optical attributes of the prepared materials. Furthermore, electrochemical response of both the PANI and PANI/g-C₃N₄ modified GCE was recorded by CV and EIS in the presence of H₂SO₄. The application of the Randles-Sevcik equation yielded the following trend in computed electroactive surface area: GCE < PANI < PANI/g-C₃N₄. The robust response characterized by a high faradic current and a substantial area suggests that these materials are well-suited for further investigation in the field of super-capacitor studies

Foul-resistant PANI/GO/Cu₂O Nanocomposite for Highly Sensitive Electrochemical Phenol Detection

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ABSTRACT

This study outlines the development of an innovative electrochemical sensor platform designed for the precise and selective detection of phenol in water, arising from industrial applications. The researchers synthesized PANI/GO/Cu₂O ternary nanocomposites using an in-situ oxidation method at low temperature. The nanocomposites were characterized by FTIR, powdered XRD, SEM, and UV-Visible spectroscopy. In crafting the sensor platform, a glassy carbon electrode (GCE) underwent modification with polyaniline/graphene oxide/cuprous oxide (PANI/GO/Cu₂O) nanocomposites under optimal conditions. Subsequently, the resultant electrode was utilized for selective detection of phenol through cyclic voltammetry (CV), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and chronoamperometry (CA). The PANI/GO/Cu₂O electrode exhibited excellent sensitivity, with a value of 0.015 $\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{M}$. Moreover, the sensor demonstrated long-term stability, ensuring its reliability over extended periods of use. Importantly, the fabricated sensor showed high selectivity for phenol detection, even in the presence of potential interferents such as Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Fe²⁺, Al²⁺, SO₄²⁻, hydroquinone and 2-naphthol. This specificity holds significant importance for safeguarding human health and monitoring environmental safety.

Keywords: Phenol, environmental effluents, nanocomposites selectivity, limit of detection.

Recent Advances in Mycelium based green composites, A Future Sustainable Biomass

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ABSTRACT

Mycelium-based green composites (MBCs) represent an eco-friendly material innovation with diverse Applications As global population increase and rapid urbanization have led to high consumer demand the raw materials manufacturing of synthetic material usually generate a large amount of waste adversely affect environment. Fungi are one of the key biological resources that can be used to develop a wide range of sustainable products including biodegradable materials with promising applications, with zero waste generation during the production process. One of them is Mycelium based composites MCBs.

PVDF-Based Piezo-Catalytic Membranes—A Net-Zero Emission Approach towards Textile Wastewater Purification

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ABSTRACT

Nano-fillers in PVDF-based catalytic membranes enhance catalytic activity and induce beta phase formation, revolutionizing wastewater treatment. These membranes promise efficient pollutant degradation, paving the path towards net-zero emissions. Besides environmental benefits, their scalability and efficacy offer significant social and commercial impacts, driving sustainable practices and supporting global initiatives.

Structure-Based Designing, Solvent Less Synthesis of 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate Derivatives: A Combined In Vitro and In Silico Screening Approach

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ABSTRACT

In this study, small molecules possessing tetrahydropyrimidine derivatives have been synthesized having halogenated benzyl derivatives and carboxylate linkage. As previously reported, FDA approved halogenated pyrimidine derivatives prompted us to synthesize novel compounds in order to evaluate their biological potential. Eight pyrimidine derivatives have been synthesized from ethyl acetoacetate, secondary amine, aromatic benzaldehyde by adding catalytic amount of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ via solvent less Grindstone multicomponent reagent method. Molecular structure reactivity and virtual screening were performed to check their biological efficacy as an anti-oxidant, anti-cancer and anti-diabetic agent. These studies were supported by in vitro analysis and QSAR studies. After combined experimental and virtual screening 5c, 5g and 5e could serve as lead compounds, having low IC_{50} and high binding affinity.

Keywords: pyrimidine, solvent less, in silico, in vitro, QSAR, DFT, MTT, molecular docking

Relationship between Excessive Social Media use and Body Dissatisfaction among Young Adults

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to investigate the relationship between excessive social media use and body dissatisfaction among young adults. It was hypothesized that (i) High levels of social media use will be positively predicted body dissatisfaction; (ii) Coping styles will significantly mediate the relationship with body dissatisfaction; (iii) Women will have higher scores of body dissatisfaction as compared to men. The total participants (N=300) were selected with age ranges (18-25 years). Research variables were measured by using Body Shape Questionnaire for Men (BSQ-34) (Cooper et al., 1987), Body Shape Questionnaire for Women (BSQ-34) (Cooper et al., 1987), Brief - Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced Inventory (Brief-COPE) (Carver, 1997), Social Media Addiction Scale (SMAS) (Al-Menayes, 2015), and a demographic sheet were used for data collection through survey method. The study findings accepted the hypotheses and found that social media excessive use was significantly positively predicted to body dissatisfaction. Women had more internalization of body dissatisfaction than men. The conceptual model revealed that mediating role of coping styles was predicting body dissatisfaction through social media excessive use. The direct effect indicated that social media overuse was significantly predicted body dissatisfaction. The indirect effects further provided a significant mediation effect of coping styles on the association between social media excessive use and body dissatisfaction. The results of the current research can be utilized for future exploration and learning practice. Adults may compare themselves along standards of appearance as propagated by family, peers, media, thin body ideal, etc. and develop body dissatisfaction problems. In current study family and media role were found significant in body dissatisfaction. It suggests to psycho-educate of family about significance of internalizations of such messages in developing mental health problems later and guide them in using positive coping strategies to combat issue of internalization. Awareness programs about appearance related messages and their internalization can be launched in school setting for better upbringing in upcoming generation to control such messages at their end which effect other's lives.

Keywords: Excessive social media use, Body dissatisfaction, coping styles, data collection, internalization, direct effect.

Relationship of Tetrad Dark Personality Traits and Delinquent Behavior Among Adolescents: Moderating Role of Social Support

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ABSTRACT

The current research examines the connection between Dark Triad personality dimensions: Machiavellianism, narcissism, psychopathy, sadism, and delinquency in adolescence while considering the role of social support as the moderator. For this study the cross-sectional research design was used, and the sample included 300 adolescents comprising 150 males and 150 females in the age group of 10 to 19 years randomly selected from twin cities of Islamabad and Rawalpindi. The data were collected using the Short Dark Tetrad (SD4) self-reported delinquency – Problem Behavior Frequency Scale and Child and Adolescent Social Support Scale (CASSS). The analyses conducted brought out positive and significant correlations between the dark personality traits and the delinquent behaviors with each of the dark personality traits being positively correlated with the manifests of delinquent behavior. Furthermore, the study revealed that social support acted as a moderator that could help decrease the delinquency rate among the adolescents who possess a high level of dark personality traits. These imply that dark personality facets and insufficient social support should be targeted to reduce delinquency among adolescents. The results imply that any prevention or treatment programs targeted at decreasing delinquency must consider the presence of dark personality features in adolescents, especially through modulating the perceived usefulness of social support. The insights from the research can be quite useful for schools, families, and community-oriented programs to design effective interventions not only to address behavior management but also to address the potentially detrimental effects associated with these personality traits.

Keywords: Delinquency, Sadism, Psychopathy, Machiavellianism, Narcissism, Social

SOCIAL SCIENCES

Linguistic Translation and Validation of Appearance Schema Inventory–Revised in Pakistani Culture

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of conducting this research study was to translate and validate the Appearance Schema Inventory–Revised (Thomas F. Cash, 2004). The sample comprised of university students (N=346) of public and private university of twin cities (Islamabad & Rawalpindi) of Pakistan, age range is 20–27years. Forward and Backward Translation was done by bilingual experts followed by approval of final version of translation by Subject Matter Experts (SMEs). To establish psychometric properties of translated Urdu version Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was carried out. The CFA results supported the two-factor structure like the original version of ASI-R with indexes of CFI=0.91, TLI=0.90 & SRMR=0.07. The alpha reliability of Urdu version of scale is .89, for subscales Self Evaluative Salience is .94 and Motivational Salience is .94. The translated version of scale has high reliability and validity and is consistent with original version of ASI-R.

Keywords: Appearance Schema Inventory–Revised (ASI-R), Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), Self-Evaluative Salience, Motivational Salience, Forward & Backward Translation

Care Giver Burden, Coping Strategies and Quality of Life of Mothers Raising Children with Autism

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ABSTRACT

The well-being of mothers raising children with Autism is essential not only for their own mental health but also for the overall quality of life of their families. The current study aimed to examine the link between caregiver burden, coping strategies and quality of life of mothers raising children with Autism. Additionally, the role of coping strategies as a mediator between caregiver burden and quality of life was investigated. The study included a total of 65 mothers as primary caregivers of children with Autism, approached through purposive sampling from autism resource centers in Islamabad. For the data collection, three self-reporting scales were administered. Care Giver Burden Scale, Quality of Life Scale and Brief Coping Health Inventory (short form) for Parents. Utilizing a mediation analysis, findings revealed that caregiver burden negatively impacts quality of life both directly and indirectly through its effect on coping strategies. Specifically, the significant interaction term between caregiver burden, coping strategies, and quality of life suggests that the effect of caregiver burden on quality of life is reduced by the effectiveness of coping strategies. The model explains fifty four percent variance in quality of life, with a highly significant fit, demonstrating strong support for the model. Correlation analyses indicate that higher caregiver burden is correlated with less effective coping strategies and a decreased quality of life, highlighting the importance of both reducing caregiver burden and enhancing coping strategies. These results underline the need for directed interventions that address caregiver burden and improve coping mechanisms to enhance the overall well-being of these mothers as immediate caregivers. The study provides valuable insights for developing comprehensive support programs aimed at improving quality of life for mothers of autistic children.

Keywords: Caregiver burden, Coping strategies, Quality of life, Autism, Caregiver support Cognitive Flexibility, Compassion Fatigue and Psychological well-being among Surgeons

Cognitive Flexibility, Compassion Fatigue and Psychological well-being among Surgeons

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationships between cognitive flexibility, compassion fatigue, and psychological well-being among surgeons, a group that operates under high-stress conditions. Cognitive flexibility, a crucial psychological trait, enables surgeons to adapt their thinking and behavior to the unpredictable nature of their work. This flexibility is essential for maintaining high standards of patient care and managing stress. Compassion fatigue, a form of emotional and physical exhaustion due to prolonged exposure to patients' suffering, significantly impacts surgeons' empathy and job satisfaction. The study utilized a cross-sectional design, surveying a sample of surgeons to assess these variables. Instruments included the Cognitive Flexibility Inventory, the Compassion Fatigue Self-Test, and the Psychological Well-being Scale. Results indicated a strong positive correlation between cognitive flexibility and psychological well-being, and a negative correlation between compassion fatigue and both cognitive flexibility and well-being. These findings suggest that enhancing cognitive flexibility may be an effective strategy for mitigating compassion fatigue and promoting well-being among surgeons. The study underscores the importance of psychological interventions aimed at improving cognitive flexibility to support surgeons in managing the demands of their profession.

Keywords: Cognitive Flexibility, Compassion Fatigue, Psychological Well-being, Surgeons, Mental Health.

Perceived Parental Rejection and Humanization of Care Among Mental Health Professionals: Mediating Role of Moral Sensitivity

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ABSTRACT

Despite the increasing interest in the influence of one's experiences with their parents on work-related factors, there has been relatively little research focused on mental health professionals. The current study aimed to examine the relationship between parental rejection in childhood perceived by mental health professionals and the level of humanized patient care provided by them, as mediated by their level of moral sensitivity. The current study involved a total of 198 mental health professionals (psychiatrists and psychologists), approached through purposive sampling, from hospitals, clinics, and rehabilitation centers based in Islamabad/Rawalpindi. For the data collection, they responded to the adult version of the Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (short form) for mothers and fathers (R. Rohner, 2004), the Moral Sensitivity Questionnaire (Takizawa et al., 2021), and the Healthcare Professional Humanization Scale (HUMAS) (M. D. C. Pérez-Fuentes et al., 2019). Results showed that maternal rejection perceived by mental health professionals in childhood significantly and negatively predicted the level of humanized patient care provided by them while perceived paternal rejection was not a significant predictor. Moreover, Moral sensitivity partially mediated the effect of perceived maternal rejection on the level of humanized patient care provided by mental health professionals. Overall, the results suggest that maternal rejection perceived by mental health professionals in childhood is likely to be associated with the decrease in the level of humanized patient care. This research helps us understand how the professional behavior of mental health professionals is influenced by their experiences with their parents, aiding in the development of interventions and training programs aimed at mitigating the harmful impacts of parental rejection and increasing their moral sensitivity/commitment towards providing humanized patient care. The study, carried out in Pakistan, also highlights cross-cultural differences in variables namely Parental Rejection, Moral Sensitivity and Humanization of Care among mental health professionals.

Keywords: Acceptance-rejection syndrome; Interpersonal acceptance-rejection theory; Humanization of Care; Moral Sensitivity.

Poor sleep quality and cognitive decline: The mediating role of emotional regulation in women with severe menopausal symptoms

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to explore the relationship between poor sleep quality, cognitive decline and how emotional regulation plays a mediating role in the relationship of variables. The study investigated the relationship of variables (age, gender, occupation, education, employment, family structure, and marital status) in this study. Through purposive sampling technique, 300 participants, taken by G*Power, were taken from academic institutes and hospitals of Islamabad, and Rawalpindi. The study used the Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) to screen-out the participants with higher menopausal symptoms. They were then assessed using the Sleep Quality Scale, Cognitive Self-Assessment Rating Scale, and Emotion Regulation Questionnaire. The study used correlation, t-tests, and mediation analysis to test the relationship between variables. The findings of this study revealed that there exist statistically significant differences in ERQ scores, with doctors showing slightly lower emotional regulation ($M = 19$, $SD = 5.07$) compared to academicians ($M = 22$, $SD = 6.51$). The descriptive statistics and correlation coefficients revealed that poor sleep quality (SQS) is positively correlated with cognitive decline (CSARS) ($r = .299$, $p < .01$). Furthermore, poor sleep quality is negatively correlated with emotional regulation (ERQ) ($r = -.205$, $p < .01$). Similarly, cognitive decline shows a negative correlation with emotional regulation ($r = -.809$, $p < .01$). The study found a positive correlation between poor sleep quality and cognitive decline, with poorer sleep quality causing more decline. Conversely, higher emotional regulation led to a decrease in cognitive decline. Emotional regulation partially mediated the effect of sleep quality on cognitive decline, as demonstrated by the mediation analysis.

Keywords: Mediation, sleep quality, cognitive decline, emotional regulation, menopause

Adolescent Gender and Age differences in Self-Regulation

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ABSTRACT

Self-regulation has been regarded as a risk and protective factor for mental health in adolescents. The aim of present research was to explore age and gender related differences in behavioral, emotional and cognitive regulation skills in Pakistani adolescents. A cross-sectional survey research design was used. Convenience sampling was used to collect data from (N=407) adolescents from 11 to 18 years of age from various major cities of Pakistan. Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Functions (BRIEF) was used to measure self-regulation along with certain demographic characteristics including school type, parents' education, location of home. Results indicated that there were significant age differences in cognitive regulation but not in emotional and behavioral regulation. There were significant gender differences in emotional and behavioral regulation. There were also significant differences in emotional and behavioral regulation between public and private schools. Results holds implication for future intervention and prevention-based research.

Keywords: Emotional regulation, cognitive regulation, behavioral regulation

Relationship between Excessive Social Media use and Body Dissatisfaction among Young Adults

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to investigate the relationship between excessive social media use and body dissatisfaction among young adults. It was hypothesized that (i) High levels of social media use will be positively predicted body dissatisfaction; (ii) Coping styles will significantly mediate the relationship with body dissatisfaction; (iii) Women will have higher scores of body dissatisfaction as compared to men. The total participants (N=300) were selected with age ranges (18-25 years). Research variables were measured by using Body Shape Questionnaire for Men (BSQ-34) (Cooper et al., 1987), Body Shape Questionnaire for Women (BSQ-34) (Cooper et al., 1987), Brief - Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced Inventory (Brief-COPE) (Carver, 1997), Social Media Addiction Scale (SMAS) (Al-Menayes, 2015), and a demographic sheet were used for data collection through survey method. The study findings accepted the hypotheses and found that social media excessive use was significantly positively predicted to body dissatisfaction. Women had more internalization of body dissatisfaction than men. The conceptual model revealed that mediating role of coping styles was predicting body dissatisfaction through social media excessive use. The direct effect indicated that social media overuse was significantly predicted body dissatisfaction. The indirect effects further provided a significant mediation effect of coping styles on the association between social media excessive use and body dissatisfaction. The results of the current research can be utilized for future exploration and learning practice. Adults may compare themselves along standards of appearance as propagated by family, peers, media, thin body ideal, etc. and develop body dissatisfaction problems. In current study family and media role were found significant in body dissatisfaction. It suggests to psycho-educate of family about significance of internalizations of such messages in developing mental health problems later and guide them in using positive coping strategies to combat issue of internalization. Awareness programs about appearance related messages and their internalization can be launched in school setting for better upbringing in upcoming generation to control such messages at their end which effect other's lives.

Keywords: Excessive social media use, Body dissatisfaction, coping styles, data collection, internalization, direct effect.

Relationship of Tetrad Dark Personality Traits and Delinquent Behavior Among Adolescents: Moderating Role of Social Support

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ABSTRACT

The current research examines the connection between Dark Triad personality dimensions: Machiavellianism, narcissism, psychopathy, sadism, and delinquency in adolescence while considering the role of social support as the moderator. For this study the cross-sectional research design was used, and the sample included 300 adolescents comprising 150 males and 150 females in the age group of 10 to 19 years randomly selected from twin cities of Islamabad and Rawalpindi. The data were collected using the Short Dark Tetrad (SD4) self-reported delinquency – Problem Behavior Frequency Scale and Child and Adolescent Social Support Scale (CASSS). The analyses conducted brought out positive and significant correlations between the dark personality traits and the delinquent behaviors with each of the dark personality traits being positively correlated with the manifests of delinquent behavior. Furthermore, the study revealed that social support acted as a moderator that could help decrease the delinquency rate among the adolescents who possess a high level of dark personality traits. These imply that dark personality facets and insufficient social support should be targeted to reduce delinquency among adolescents. The results imply that any prevention or treatment programs targeted at decreasing delinquency must consider the presence of dark personality features in adolescents, especially through modulating the perceived usefulness of social support. The insights from the research can be quite useful for schools, families, and community-oriented programs to design effective interventions not only to address behavior management but also to address the potentially detrimental effects associated with these personality traits.

Keywords: Delinquency, Sadism, Psychopathy, Machiavellianism, Narcissism, Social

Unveiling the Potential: Analyzing Trends of Character Strengths among Pakistani Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Adolescence has long been viewed as a stage of storm and stress. This conceptualization has led to focus primarily on the problems associated with this life-stage. In line with the recent shift towards prevention science and positive psychology, there emerges a need to study adolescence from a strength-based perspective. It can help in gaining a holistic understanding of this population by focusing on their existing resources that can be utilized further for promoting their wellbeing. In this regard, the Classification of Strengths and Virtues has been an extensively researched model that focuses on one's strengths by finding the answer to 'what's best in people' and its impact on their wellbeing. This study has aimed to assess the trends of these character strengths among Pakistani adolescents aged 13 to 17 years. Values in Action Inventory of Character Strengths - Youth Survey (VIA-YR2) was conducted on 500 participants, recruited from schools of Rawalpindi/Islamabad using cluster random sampling. Findings revealed that constructs of Appreciation of Beauty and Excellence, Love, Hope, Creativity, and Love of Learning appeared as the highest whereas Humility, Self-regulation, Fairness, Zest, and Honesty were the lowest prevalent strengths among the participants. Both genders presented a similar pattern of strengths apart from females displaying gratitude instead of love of learning as one of their highest strengths. Group comparison shows that females scored higher on character strengths as compared to males except for the self-regulation. These findings can be utilized in designing and implementing interventions that can foster the well-being of adolescents.

Keywords: Adolescence, Character Strengths, Positive Psychology, Well-being

Climate Change and Human Rights: Case Study of Climate prone Human Crisis in Pakistan (2001-2024)

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ABSTRACT

Global community in the terrestrial sphere is causing existential threats from climate change. The horrific proposition of climate change is not exclusively confined to loss of biodiversity, food deficit or loss of natural resources, additionally fundamental injustice, ethical issues and human rights violation. Article highlights that historically, climate debate was constrained to disruption natural ecosystem and infringement of right to health, nevertheless, at this juncture climate change has engendered the trepidation among humans as it subverts the aptitude to advocate and implement human rights, distinctly right to live. In this article, mixed methodology will be employed. Article ascertains that climate change is exerting an impact on the humans disproportionately across both low-income and high-income countries. Those living in multitude of low-income states are contingent to the dismal impacts of climate change even though they have contributed negligibly to the problem. Furthermore, low-income countries have the fewest resources and capabilities at contemporary to adapt or cope with the severe. Building on human rights principles of accountability and redress for human rights violations, this paper responds to this injustice by seeking to make long-neglected societal amends through the implementation of the notion of climate reparations. After discussing the scientific evidence for climate change, its environmental and socioeconomic ramifications, and the ethical and human rights justifications for climate reparations, the paper proposes the creation of a new global institutional mechanism, the Global Climate Reparations Fund, which would be associated with the United Nations Human Rights Council, to fund and initiate measures on climate reparations.

Keywords: Climate, Change, Human, rights, Pakistan

Eco-friendly Energy Mix and Energy Affordability: An Energy Policy-Step towards Energy Security in Pakistan (2001-2024)

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ABSTRACT

This research paper examines the intersection of eco-friendly energy solutions, energy affordability, and energy security within the context of Pakistan's energy sector from 2014 to 2024. Despite possessing abundant renewable energy resources including solar, wind and hydel, Pakistan has grappled with energy insecurity and affordability issues stemming from over-reliance on imported fossil fuels including furnace oil, LNG and imported coal. Through a comprehensive analysis of policy measures, technological advancements, and socioeconomic factors, this paper evaluates the efficacy of transitioning towards an eco-friendly energy mix as a means to achieve energy security while ensuring affordability for consumers. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, incorporating qualitative analysis of energy policies and quantitative assessments of energy affordability indices and renewable energy utilization trends. The study will also focus on how diversified energy portfolio, incorporating renewables such as solar, wind, and hydroelectric power, can mitigate energy vulnerabilities, reduce dependency on imported fuels, and promote environmental sustainability. Furthermore, the study will also highlight the impact of CPEC projects particularly its environmental implications and issue of capacity payment's which alarmingly created affordability challenges. Study will also assess Pakistan plans to utilize rich indigenous Thar Coal and considers the shifting of ongoing imported coal fired plants on Thar coal which will reduce cost significantly.

Keywords: Energy, Security, Eco-friendly, Affordability, Policy, Pakistan

Exploring the relationship between Gig Economy and Employment Stability in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

It is currently essential to look into alternative employment models due to the rise in joblessness, financial uncertainty, and the shortcomings of traditional employment systems. Such serious issues seemed to have a solution in the "gig economy," which is characterized by numerous and versatile employment possibilities. This study explores the relationship between employment stability and gig economy participation, emphasizing the moderating influence of technology advancement and the mediating role of job creation. The study looks at the gig economy's historical background and current rapid growth, especially in Pakistan, where there are few job opportunities and the gig economy provides a vital safety net for youngsters with no jobs. The study looks at how artificial intelligence and technological advancements support the growth of the gig economy within the aim to show that gig work and stable employment are positively correlated. The findings are intended to highlight the gig economy's potential to stabilize employment rates, create global channels, and offer reliable sources of income. This study points out the revolutionary effects of the gig economy on youth unemployment and fostering economic growth in Pakistan. In conclusion, adopting the gig economy could boost financial stability, promote innovative thinking, and widen the range of opportunities for employment, offering meaningful and lasting benefits to the labor force and individuals nationwide.

Keywords: Gig Economy, Employment Stability, Job Creation, Technological Advancements, Youth Unemployment, Economic Growth, Pakistan

Sustainable Remote Work: Creating Green Jobs through Freelancing for a Sustainable Environment

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ABSTRACT

Traditional employment practices contribute to environmental issues like greenhouse gas emissions, global warming, and climate change, especially because of factors related to transportation. These problems represent a threat to the environment, but they also make it harder for the labor market to adjust to shifting economic conditions, which drives up unemployment rates. Finding alternative employment models becomes more and more important in this situation. The freelance economy presents itself as a feasible solution, providing a range of employment options that can lessen negative effects on environment. This study explores the connection between freelancing and a sustainable environment, highlighting the contributions of job creation.

Based on primary data collected through questionnaires, which yielded 616 responses, descriptive statistics reveal that freelancing positively impacts environmental sustainability. The average mean for freelancing participation is 5.8417, with a standard deviation of 1.92584, indicating high engagement in remote work. Respondents strongly agree that freelancing contributes to a cleaner environment while providing a stable source of income. A sustainable environment's mean value (the dependent variable) is 2.4127, and its standard deviation is 0.41473. This suggests that participants feel safe working as independent contractors and making a positive environmental impact. The high rate of freelancing lowers the carbon footprint associated with traditional employment, demonstrating the economy's potential to stabilize jobs and encourage environmentally friendly behavior. In summary, adopting a freelance career can foster creative problem-solving, and increase employment opportunities—all of which have a significant positive impact on the labor force. The freelancing sector can effectively drive economic growth while addressing climate change and its impacts by prioritizing environmental sustainability alongside job creation.

Keywords: Freelancing, Sustainable Environment, Job Creation, Remote Work, Carbon footprints, Green Jobs

Enhancing Understanding of Science Concepts through Metacognitive Strategies: A Student-Centric Paradigm

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the efficacy of leveraging metacognitive strategies to improve students' comprehension of science concepts in education. Thirty secondary level science students from a private school in Chiniot city participated in a research initiative utilizing a pre-test and post-test design. The assessments comprised 15 short conceptual questions related to 9th-grade physics, specifically focusing on the domains of kinematics and dynamics. Employing a student-centered approach guided by the Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI), participants engaged in a reflective process to identify areas of uncertainty and implement targeted metacognitive strategies. These strategies included setting clear learning objectives, monitoring understanding during class activities and independent study, seeking clarification when encountering challenges, and reflecting on the effectiveness of learning approaches. Quantitative analysis revealed a significant improvement in participants' post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores: Pre-test Mean Score: 61 ± 7 SD, Post-test Mean Score: 80 ± 5 SD. Statistical analysis using paired t-test revealed a significant improvement in participants' post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores ($p < 0.001$), indicating enhanced comprehension of science concepts. The findings underscore the pivotal role of metacognitive strategies in fostering student learning and comprehension of complex scientific concepts. Implications for instructional practices and recommendations for future research are discussed.

Keywords: Science Concepts, Assessment, Metacognitive Strategies, Academic Achievement, Metacognitive Awareness Inventory.

Exploring the Transformative Role of ChatGPT in Higher Education: Impacts on Teaching, Research, Assessment, and Learning Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has become a focal point of discussion among educators and researchers in Pakistan. ChatGPT, a generative AI developed by Open AI, exemplifies this trend, offering transformative potential for teaching, learning, research, and assessment in higher education. This study explores the dynamic impact of ChatGPT, and its advantages and challenges within the Pakistani higher education setting. The aim of this study is to explore how ChatGPT is reshaping the landscape of higher education in Pakistan. This research employs a qualitative design, utilizing semi-structured interviews with twelve experienced academicians from higher education institutions across Pakistan. This approach allows to collect data for an exploratory study to explain any phenomenon at an initial level. Through the ChatGPT thematic analysis of the interviews, we discovered five main themes: teaching, learning, assessment, research, and ethics. The findings indicate that ChatGPT can significantly enhance educational productivity, foster creativity, and facilitate idea generation. However, concerns about academic honesty, the potential for over-reliance on ChatGPT, and the need for ethical guidelines were also prominent. The study underscores the necessity for educators and

policymakers to navigate these challenges while leveraging the benefits of ChatGPT. While, ChatGPT can enhance productivity, creativity, and learning outcomes, educators must navigate issues of academic integrity and over-reliance on AI-generated content. Responsible integration of ChatGPT requires developing ethical guidelines and policies to ensure its effective and ethical use in academic settings.

Keywords: ChatGPT; Generative AI; Education; Learning; Teaching; Research; Assessment; Ethical Considerations

A Study of Change in Co-curricular Activities for Leadership Development among Secondary School Students

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ABSTRACT

The research in the area of leadership considers it highly important to develop leadership skills among secondary school students in order to make them successful in future (Chen, 2017; Lin, Ma, Yu, Leung, Wu & Dou, 2021). Extra-curricular activities are often related to the development of leadership skills among students (Chen, 2017). In this qualitative study, the researcher intends to explore knowledge related to leadership development through co-curricular activities. Phenomenological research design is used to examine “lived experiences” of the participants, principals of the government and private secondary schools, related to the phenomenon. Analysis of the perception and experiences of the principals from both sectors revealed that development of leadership skills is very essential for students at secondary level and co-curricular activities play a significant role in their development. However, co-curricular plan at secondary level faces hurdles due to lack of human, spatial and financial resources, especially in public schools. It is suggested that an activity-based leadership development programmed should be initiated at secondary level in government as well as in all private schools.

Keywords: co-curricular activities, leadership development, life skills, social skills, secondary school students

Knowledge, perception, and awareness about Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among university students: A case study of University of Wah.

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ABSTRACT

The new paradigm of education for Sustainable Human Development has arisen recently and it includes several key concepts like Human Development (HD) as the process of expansion of capabilities and real freedoms that people enjoy, another concept is Sustainable Development (SD) which can be defined as current development that does not jeopardize the development of future generations, Sustainable Human Development (SHD) can be termed as: "the expansion of the substantive freedoms of people today while making reasonable efforts to avoid seriously compromising those of future generations" Education for Sustainable Human Development (ESHD) seeks to generate processes that qualify for SHD in all sectors of the population, covering both formal and informal education spaces.

University has a crucial role in achieving SD and SHD. There are different visions of university: a producer of economic values, university as a social elevator; and university committed to building a fairer world. It is right now a symbol of globalization, so it is essential to train students in competences that enable them to be global citizens. Numerous initiatives have been carried out in the field of teaching to promote SHD at the university level. There are different methodologies to carry out this task. In each one of these areas, the university can contribute to the construction of a fairer society and, therefore, to the construction of the SDGs. As the higher education contributes decisively to the SDGs implementation in the globe and these institutions can take on the role of a liaison between different stakeholder groups. Higher education institutions have a particular responsibility to form future professionals and implement the knowledge and ideas so that the purpose of conducting this research is to explore the perception of university students about the knowledge and understanding about SDGs at University of Wah.

Keywords: Globalization, SDG's, Sustainable human development.

Teachers' Perceptions about Physical and Learning Environment of the Classroom at Private Schools

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ABSTRACT

This research has been conducted to know the opinion of teachers about classroom's physical and learning environment and its impact on students learning at private schools of Punjab. School and its environment are integral part of student life. School is a place where a child spends its precious time. It should be equipped with all necessary facilities which help him to grow. The research hypothesized the difference between opinion of the teachers based on various demographical variables. A cross sectional Quantitative survey research design has been selected to conduct the research, and data was collected through a questionnaire which consists of two parts, physical environment and learning environment having 14 items in each part. A total of 191 male and female teachers from private schools were the sample in this study. To analysis the data SPSS software was used. One sample t test, independent sample t test and ANOVA was applied. The study revealed that teachers are not much satisfied with the physical and learning environment of the schools. The study suggested measures for the improvement of the infrastructure and environment.

Keywords: Teacher perceptions, Classroom, Physical and Learning Environment

Contribution of FPDA to Deconstruct the Traditional Gender Roles and Practices

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ABSTRACT

Feminist Post-structural Discourse Analysis (FPDA) is an evolutionary approach to study gender and language in practice. It is the outcome of the combination of discourse and post-structuralism which has been designed for the power relations associated with gender. "Discourse is a conceived set of beliefs and understandings, reinforced through daily practices, which frame a particular understanding of the ways we are in the world" (Weedon, 2004). The study offers a valuable approach to challenge the fashionable and entrenched practices to bring positive change in the society. Moreover, it provides multiple ways for women to practice their power in a way that is acceptable in the society. As media plays a pivotal role in constructing and deconstructing the mind-set of the people of every age group, therefore a prominent and highly used platform of animated movie 'Brave' is utilized for the current study to present a qualitative analysis covering all the possible presented forums of discourse to portray a beautiful and different perspective of molding human mind and their practices which gives a break from a rising conflict between different genders. It proposed the idea of deconstructing the old school of thought and constructing a flexible ideology for both genders which provides more space of equal opportunities and role plays in the society.

Keywords: Deconstruction, Evolutionary mind-set, Media and portrayal of norms and practices, Gender and role plays, Challenge and acceptance

Enhancing Cybersecurity in Pakistan's Nuclear Infrastructure: Addressing Emerging Digital Threats

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ABSTRACT

As countries enhance their nuclear capabilities, it is crucial to prioritize the protection of key Infrastructure, especially considering the increasing cyber threats. This project aims to strengthen Pakistan's nuclear future by addressing cybersecurity concerns in its nuclear infrastructure. An In-depth investigation is conducted to assess the present cybersecurity situation, pinpointing Specific threats and weaknesses that are distinct to nuclear sites. The focus is on evaluating the Regulatory framework to determine its effectiveness and suggesting improvements to strengthen Cybersecurity safeguards. The study incorporates a risk assessment that considers technological and human variables, and proposes techniques for efficient risk management. Investigating Advanced technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning is a crucial aspect of the Suggested security measures. The text examines how international cooperation, public Awareness, and good communication may strengthen nuclear cybersecurity. The qualitative Approach is adopted in order to conduct this research. This report provides valuable insights on Protecting nuclear assets from new cyber risks, including practical suggestions for policymakers, Regulatory agencies, and nuclear site operators.

Keywords: Nuclear infrastructure, Cyber Security, Nuclear Security, Nuclear future

Exploring the Socioeconomic Issues Faced by Young Offenders on Probation in Peshawar

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ABSTRACT

Young offenders on probation face numerous socioeconomic challenges that can significantly impact their lives. These concerns are particularly prominent in Peshawar, Pakistan, which requires comprehensive investigation in order to understand and effectively resolve them. This study aimed to identify the socioeconomic issues faced by young offenders on probation and explore their impact on the rehabilitation process of young offenders. The research questions were: What are the primary socioeconomic issues faced by young offenders on probation in Peshawar? How are these socioeconomic issues affecting the rehabilitation process? This study used a qualitative research method, focusing on gathering insights through interviews with 20 young probationers, from the District Probation Office in Peshawar. Respondents were selected using the purposive sampling technique. The data was analyzed by thematic analysis, and ethical measures were taken to maintain respondent's anonymity. This research was conducted on a small selected sample from male young offenders in Peshawar, so it cannot be generalized to all young offenders in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The study found that young offenders on probation encounter socioeconomic challenges that hinder their rehabilitation and reintegration. The presence of stigma, feelings of isolation and strained family relationships inhibit their ability to develop a positive identity and receive the necessary support. Community acceptance plays a vital role in ensuring that individuals on probation can reintegrate into society. The financial challenges associated with probation can affect job stability, handling of debts and overall quality of life. Therefore, specific initiatives are necessary to improve probation services and ensure positive reintegration outcomes.

Keywords: Young offenders, Probation, Socioeconomic issues, Rehabilitation, Peshawar.

IMF's Structural Adjustment Programs and Its Impact on Women's Socioeconomic Empowerment in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

This research systematically explores the Gendered impact of the International Monetary Fund's (IMF) Structural Adjustment Programs (SAPs) in relation to the Pakistani women by pointing out how, SAPs deepen women's vulnerability in an economy that was already unfriendly to them. Based on a mixed-methods approach that allows quantitative analysis of national survey data with qualitative interviews survey conducted with women from different marginalised groups and key-informant interviews with policymakers and specialists, the study explores how SAPs, intended for macroeconomic stabilization, are damaging for the majority of women. Restructuring of economy through SAPs accompanied by cut on spending on health, education, and social services, are areas, which are very important for women's development. The economic restructuring that has been forced has led to the women being left jobless, poor accessibility to the economic capitals, and additional and increased domestic duties as social assistance has been cut. SAPs adverse impacts underscore how they amplify any form of discrimination against women within societies, leaving the worst affected women in even worse off and socially excluded. The study explores the SAPs' ability to effectively facilitate change and advocates for the inclusion of gender-sensitive policies to promote and enhance women's needs and rights for equitable economic growth. These observations are crucial for those politicians and members of international financial organizations who decided on the pursuit of true socioeconomic development for all population groups.

Impact of China's Investment in Gwadar Port on Local Pakistani Businesses: Economic Benefits, Challenges, and Perceptions

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ABSTRACT

China's investment in Gwadar Port significantly alters regional trade dynamics, presenting opportunities and challenges for local Pakistani businesses and the broader maritime routes in the Indian Ocean. This research aims to evaluate the economic impact of Gwadar Port on local enterprises, assess its strategic importance, and analyze the perceptions of Pakistani people in business regarding China's involvement. This study uses Dependency Theory to explore the potential dynamics of neocolonial relationships between China and Pakistan. Despite extensive literature on Gwadar's strategic and macroeconomic significance within the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), there is a notable gap concerning the direct impact on local businesses. This research addresses this gap through quantitative methodology. It employs structured questionnaires to gather data from Pakistani businessmen in Gwadar and its surroundings. The findings will offer insights into the economic activities influenced by the port's development, highlighting the perceived benefits and risks of local entrepreneurs. Statistical analysis will identify trends and correlations, providing a comprehensive understanding of Gwadar's influence on local business and its broader regional impact. This study contributes to a nuanced understanding of how significant infrastructural investments affect local economies and business landscapes.

Keywords: China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), Local Pakistani Businesses, Regional Trade Dynamics, Business Perceptions, Economic Impact

Impact of Social Media Usage on Happiness and Well-being among Adolescents and Young Adults

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of social media usage on happiness and well-being among Pakistani adolescents and young adults in the urban areas of Lahore. The aim was to understand how social media influences their mental health and overall life satisfaction. Using a quantitative research design, data were collected through a structured online survey. The sample comprised 200 individuals aged 15 to 24, selected through stratified random sampling to ensure representation across different socioeconomic backgrounds within Lahore. The survey included measures of social media usage patterns, self-reported happiness, and well-being indicators. Results indicated a significant correlation between high social media usage and decreased levels of happiness and well-being, with negative effects more pronounced among females and individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Conversely, moderate social media use was associated with enhanced social connectivity and access to support networks, contributing positively to well-being. The findings suggest that while excessive social media use can detrimentally affect mental health, balanced usage can offer social benefits. The study concluded that stakeholders, including parents, educators, and policymakers, should promote healthy social media habits to mitigate adverse effects and enhance the positive aspects of social media engagement. These results underscore the need for tailored interventions to address the unique challenges faced by Pakistani youth in the digital age.

Keywords: Social media usage, happiness, well-being, mental health, social connectivity, digital age, urban areas

Navigating Minds: Socio-Cultural Influences on Mental Health in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the complex relationships that exist between socio-cultural patterns of society and how it is influenced student's mental well-being. Mental health is an essential as it's influenced learning, teaching, relationship and overall academic success. Employing quantitative approach, a self-administered questionnaire survey was conducted for data collection. A multistage sampling was utilized to gather data from student population of sample size 322. The research combined descriptive and inferential analysis to understand these complex dynamics. The descriptive statistics provide a comprehensive profile of study population to illuminate socio-cultural patterns and inferential analysis reveals the relationship of socio-cultural patterns with mental health of students. The results showed that economic factors had a great influence on mental health of students. The students from lower-economic class have high mental health outcomes then those who are from high socio-economic class (p-value: 0.000, Beta Coefficient: 0.305, t-value: 5.725). Moreover, the students in culture that promotes help-seeking have lower mental health score compare to students in a culture that discourage help-seeking (p-value: 0.021, t-statistic: 2.327, coefficient 0.135). Universities can leverage these insights to develop targeted intervention that address socio-cultural issues and foster positive connections among students.

Keywords: Sociocultural Factors, Mental Health, Students, Higher Education

The Indo-Sarcenic Architectural Aesthetics of The Nawab Architecture of Bahawalpur: A Comparative Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The research leads to the study of architectural characteristics of inbuilt form and decorative elements on the surface of the Indo-Sarcenic architecture of Bahawalpur. As the Indo-Sarcenic architecture was evolved in the era of Nawab Sadiq Muhammad Khan IV, developed in the reign of Nawab Bahawal Khan V and modernized in the period of Nawab Sadiq Muhammad Khan V. After reviewing the literature, it is apparent that scholars have generally discussed the architectural monuments built in the Colonial Period, but the aesthetics of decorative elements are ignored in constructive form and on surface decoration of the Indo-Sarcenic architecture and their influences along with comparative analysis of the buildings.

The present research deals with in-depth study of the elements like Mughals, colonial and Islamic influences intermingled to develop Indo-Sarcenic architecture and develop a comparative analysis of three structures of different eras. The structure of Daulat khana (1881) will be discussed in period of Nawab Sadiq Muhammad Khan IV, Bahawal Victoria Hospital (1906) in the era of Nawab Bahawal Khan V and SD High School in (1911) from the era of Nawab Sadiq Muhammad Khan V. The aim of the research is to provide in-depth study of constructive forms like domical structures, bastions, arches, portico as well as building materials and surface decorations like floral patterns, geometrical designs will be segments of the research. Source of inspiration, regional influences will also be explored. Visuals and photographs will be attached for better understanding of the study.

Key Words: Indo Sarcenic, Mughals, Colonial, Bahawalpur.

THE ROLE OF PAKISTAN IN THE REGIONAL SECURITY – ADHERING TO THE CHINESE GEOPOLITICAL STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

“On 21st June 2024, at the third meeting of the Sino-Pakistan Joint Consultative Mechanism (JCM), the Chinese Minister of the International Department of the Communist Party of China (IDCPC) and member of the Communist Party Central Committee Liu Jian Chao underlined the imminent essentiality of internal stability for Pakistan’s journey towards peoples’ prosperity”. He emphasized the necessity of building Pakistan’s image as a responsible nation at the geopolitical stage which is confronting a dilemma since its inception in 1947 that has claimed hundreds of thousands innocent civilian lives and thousands of armed forces personnel, an irreparable loss to the nation while contemplating foreign powers’ interests. But, the first-ever historic aspect of this meeting was an extraordinary consent demonstrated by all national political parties on “the China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC)” while setting their unbridgeable differences aside. Every leader reiterated his party’s unwavering stance to further the Sino-Pakistan development projects under the umbrella of time-tested bilateral relations. This is, indeed, the most iconic development in the entire history in which Pakistan’s leaning towards China beyond a dictated level has always been considered a serious threat to the United States and its allies’ multifaceted interests in the region. Amidst this turbulent scenario of uncertainty, especially prevalent in South Asia, Pakistan already confronting internal and external security challenges, needs to voyage through turbulent waters having treacherous shores; an endeavor not to repeat its calamitous past. In the wake of extremely fragile security environment, the aim of this study paper is to highlight the efficacy of Chinese domain of International Relations encompassing their peculiar concept of regional / international security which, portraying Quaid-e-Azam’s vision for prosperous nation, is expected to resolve Pakistan’s internal / external issues related to the well-being of its people.

Keywords: The Sino-Pakistan Relation, China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), The Chinese Concept of Security

Work-Life Balance: Investigating the Socio-Emotional Development of Children with Working Mothers in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Children face several socio-emotional development effects that are the result of their mother's employment during their early developmental years (4 to 14 years old). The study aimed to assess the impact of working mothers on their children's socio-emotional development, focusing on self-awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, and interpersonal skills. A descriptive design was employed to fulfill the aim of the study. This study was conducted at a selected governmental university (the University of Sargodha) in Sargodha city. I gathered data from 100 working mothers who fulfilled the criteria for purposive sampling. A structured questionnaire sheet using a 5-point Likert scale. The mother's communication style (correlation coefficient: 0.910, $p < 0.01$), method of parenting (correlation coefficient: 0.830, $p < 0.01$), and nature of work (correlation coefficient: 0.932, $p < 0.01$) all had a positive and significant effect on the socio-emotional development of the children. The findings suggest that while maternal employment poses challenges of maintaining work-life balance and managing stress, the benefits such as financial independence, role modeling, and the potential for enhanced self-esteem far outweigh the difficulties.

Keywords: Working mother, Socio-emotional development, Nature of job, Parenting Style and Empowerment.

Sustainable Remote Work: Creating Green Jobs through Freelancing for a Sustainable Environment

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ABSTRACT

Traditional employment practices contribute to environmental issues like greenhouse gas emissions, global warming, and climate change, especially because of factors related to transportation. These problems represent a threat to the environment, but they also make it harder for the labor market to adjust to shifting economic conditions, which drives up unemployment rates. Finding alternative employment models becomes more and more important in this situation. The freelance economy presents itself as a feasible solution, providing a range of employment options that can lessen negative effects on environment. This study explores the connection between freelancing and a sustainable environment, highlighting the contributions of job creation.

Based on primary data collected through questionnaires, which yielded 616 responses, descriptive statistics reveal that freelancing positively impacts environmental sustainability. The average mean for freelancing participation is 5.8417, with a standard deviation of 1.92584, indicating high engagement in remote work. Respondents strongly agree that freelancing contributes to a cleaner environment while providing a stable source of income. A sustainable environment's mean value (the dependent variable) is 2.4127, and its standard deviation is 0.41473. This suggests that participants feel safe working as independent contractors and making a positive environmental impact. The high rate of freelancing lowers the carbon footprint associated with traditional employment, demonstrating the economy's potential to stabilize jobs and encourage environmentally friendly behavior. In summary, adopting a freelance career can foster creative problem-solving, and increase employment opportunities—all of which have a significant positive impact on the labor force. The freelancing sector can effectively drive economic growth while addressing climate change and its impacts by prioritizing environmental sustainability alongside job creation.

Keywords: Freelancing, Sustainable Environment, Job Creation, Remote Work, Carbon footprints, Green Jobs

MANAGEMENT

SCIENCES

Assessing Behavioral factors impacting Dosimeter use among Medical Radiation Workers using Psychometric Tool

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ABSTRACT

Despite the importance of personal dosimeters in ensuring radiation safety, inconsistent use persists among medical radiation workers (MRWs). This study explores the behaviors influencing dosimeter use and associated challenges in hospital settings in Pakistan. Using the psychometric tool based on Theory of planned behavior (TPB) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), we examined the attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control of MRWs. The study has employed the psychometric tool to collect data from 301 Medical Health Workers (MRWs) through self-report 5-point Likert scale questionnaire administered in their natural work environment. Purposive sampling techniques targeted MRWs engaged in radioactive tasks from selected healthcare institutes in twin cities. Our findings reveal that attitudes have a significant direct effect on the mediator (Ability to overcome Shortcomings), but not on perceived usefulness. Social factors within subjective norms have a significant direct effect, while complexity does not. The mediator (Ability to overcome shortcomings) strengthens the relationship between independent variables and perceived usefulness, except for attitudes of Ability to Perform. The results suggest that enhancing intentions through training, awareness, facilitation, and monitoring proper dosimeter usage can improve the behavior of Perceived Usefulness of Dosimeters.

Dependence Structure between NFTS's and Cryptocurrency; Evidence from Copula Approach

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the dependence structure between the crypto coins and the NFTs. We have taken data of 5 years from 2017 to 2022 and used crypto currency (Bitcoin, Ethereum & Litecoin). Through an analysis of price formation from the prices of various cryptocurrencies, the study offers fascinating insights into the possibility of NFT price prediction. The paper identifies the nature and strength of the dependence structure between NFTs and cryptocurrencies, revealing they exhibit positive dependence. Our findings indicate weak correlations and dependence structures between NFT, BNB, ETH, and BTC, with fat tail dependence in the copula modeling suggesting significant relationships between these variables.

Keywords: Cryptocurrency, NFT, Copula

Exploring the barriers to Knowledge Sharing in Public Sector Organizations using Theory of Sociocultural Models (TSCMs): A Case Study of National Institute of Management, Pakistan Academy for Rural Development and Pakistan Provincial Services Academy

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge Sharing (KS) entails sharing and transfer of explicit and tacit knowledge for collaborative problem solving and innovation. However, public sector organizations have some typical cultural barriers to KS such as strict adherence to hierarchies, lack of trust, lack of social capital, turf wars. KS is required to be nurtured in a specific cultural environment which generally encourages socialization, openness, sharing, team work, innovation etc. This research uses Theory of Sociocultural Models (TSCM) to explore the cultural communities developed by the employees of the three public sector organizations National Institute of Management (NIM) Peshawar, Pakistan Academy for Rural Development (PARD) and Pakistan Provincial Services Academy (PPSA) and identify the cultural attributes which are hampering knowledge sharing amongst the three organizations. Using person centered ethnography, semi-structured interviews and non-obtrusive participant observation it has been established that NIM, PARD, PPSA demonstrate the typical siloed approach regarding knowledge sharing despite being housed within one campus, led by one Director General and sharing the various facilities of the campus. There are significant barriers to knowledge sharing emanating from the cultural communities or SCMs developed in the NIM, PARD and PPSA which are alienated from one another despite having similar mandates of training and research. This research has added value to the limited research available on the interlinkage of bureaucratic culture and knowledge management in public sector organizations of Pakistan. The novelty of this research is the identification of the need to develop a knowledge sharing culture by reforming the bureaucratic culture prevalent in public sector organizations of Pakistan.

Keywords: Knowledge Sharing, Knowledge Management, Sociocultural Models

From Green Policies to Practices: Outcome of Green Human Resource Management on Organization Performance and HR Policies for Conventional to Become Greener

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ABSTRACT

The initial human race that took refuge in caves to survive the extremes of the seasons afterward when went on the path of industrial revolution itself became a threat to these seasons. In return the nature triggered a problem of climate change from which the modern human being contends at this moment in time. Different scholars conduct multiple studies in their area to overcome this issue and following study is also a chain of it for looks into the effect of Green Human Resource Practices on the organization performance. In this study green recruitment & selection and green training & development are used as independent variables to see its impact on organization performance which is used as a dependent variable. Data is gathered through the Primary research method (i.e. 05-Point Likert scale questionnaires) which are distributed through google survey platform to the Human Resource managers of 100 different organizational sectors inside Pakistan that currently apply these practices in their organization. Collected data is analyzed through Statistical Package for the Social Sciences and Google analysis tool. The multiple regression and correlation models are applied to see the effect among variables. After analysis, the study concluded that the variables indicated in this study have a positive significant effect on the performance of an organization. The novelty of the study is its covers managerial level (i.e. previous studies only covered employee level) as well as provides the green human resource techniques or roles that conventional organizations adopt to become "Greener".

Keywords: GHRM, Sustainable HRM, Green Management, Organization Performance, HRM Policies

Impact of Green Accounting to improve Financial Performance

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ABSTRACT

Green accounting has been shown to have a major impact on improving financial performance and business sustainability. It has been found that adopting green accounting practices has a favorable effect on financial indicators like ROA. This study used bibliometric research to demonstrate that green accounting promotes not just financial performance but also sustainability initiatives and overall corporate value.

A meta-analysis further demonstrates a high positive link between corporate financial success and environmental reporting, indicating that financially stronger corporations are typically those who disclose environmental information. The findings have significant practical implications, suggesting that businesses can enhance their financial performance by integrating green accounting principles into their operations. This alignment not only supports sustainable development goals but also offers a competitive advantage in the market.

Keywords: Green Accounting; Sustainable Development; Financial Performance

Impact of Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Engagement: The Moderating Role of Co-Worker Support

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the impact of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) on employee engagement (EE), exploring the moderating role of co-worker support. Unlike perceived organizational support the coworker support is also crucial for employee engagement. Coworker support when the employees' encounter the challenging tasks without readily available solutions. Despite having a significant importance of co-worker support very less is explored on this variable. Recognizing the importance of this fact and relationship of these variables, the present research has tried to fill this literature gap. Using a quantitative approach, the study gathered the data from 250 frontline employees in private bank twin city of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Regression analysis was conducted to analyze the data. Findings indicate a positive relationship between POS and higher levels of employee engagement, with co-worker support significantly moderating this relationship. The results suggest that employee engagement can be achieved by extending both perceived organizational support and co-worker support. This underscores the importance of fostering a supportive organizational environment and promoting strong interpersonal relationships among employees to boost engagement levels effectively.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support, Employee Engagement, Co-worker, Support

Impact of Taxes on Financial Leverage: Moderating role of Institutional Investor

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ABSTRACT

This study set out to investigate the impact of Effective Tax Rate on Financial Leverage with a moderating role of Institutional Investor in emerging economy, Pakistan. Using Modigliani and Miller theory or Trade-Off theory, this study highlights the importance of Financial Leverage with respect to Effective Tax Rate and Institutional Investor in the context of Pakistan, where information asymmetry and concentrated ownership patterns are prevalent. To investigate this, we have used secondary data from the financial statements of the top 50 non-financial listed firms on the KSE-100 index for the period 2016 to 2022. Using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), our findings suggest that Financial Leverage is positively related to Effective Tax Rate. Interestingly, our findings further reveal that Institutional Investor negatively moderates this relationship. This study provides practical implications for corporate managers, policymakers, and institutional investors. Corporate managers can enhance their capital structure decisions, policymakers can create tax laws, and investors can improve strategies of investing in developing economies.

Keywords: Financial Leverage, Effective Tax Rate, Institutional Investor, Taxes

Institutional Pressures and Corporate Governance Reforms: Effects on Earnings Management in emerging economies of Asia

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ABSTRACT

This study extant body of knowledge in accounting and finance paradigm's The author expands the comprehension of corporate governance, ownership structure (foreign and institutional investors), and earnings management by clarifying the manner in which these factors affect the earnings management practices of firms. Furthermore, this study empirically examines the institutional environment's moderating effect in case of emerging economies.

The research design utilized in this investigation was ex-post facto. Publicly listed non-financial firms on the stock exchanges of Pakistan, China, and India comprise the population. The annual data collected over a ten-year period (2010–2019) comprised 392 non-financial firms, resulting in 3920 observations. Data were obtained from firm's annual reports, which demonstrated both cross-sectional and time-series characteristics. As a result, the hypotheses were examined and validated using a panel data methodology. Although both fixed and random effect models were examined, the fixed effect model was determined to be the most suitable among the panel data techniques in numerous instances. The robust standard error method was employed to evaluate the models' robustness in relation to heteroscedasticity. The principal components approach was employed to develop indexes of corporate governance and institutional environment.

The results are consistent with the theoretical predictions and prior research. Earnings management was discovered to be substantially adversely affected by corporate governance, institutional and foreign investors. The moderating effect of institutional quality demonstrated that managerial discretionary powers are restricted by strong institutional environments, thereby reducing earnings manipulations. This research is unique in that it has not been previously tested for this specific mechanism. Additionally, it contributes to the theoretical literature on finance and accounting in this region.

Keywords: Earnings management, Corporate governance, Institutional investors, Institutional environment, Asian emerging economies

Internal Marketing and Internal Customers Satisfaction: Examining the Combined effect of Servicescape and Personal Interrelation

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ABSTRACT

Internal marketing plays an important role in improving satisfaction level of internal customer (Employees) but there are several other factors which can affect this relationship. Personal interrelation and servicescape (place in which services are provided) are two aspects among those. The objective of this study is to access and understand that how internal marketing affects the satisfaction of internal customers i.e. employees. The other dimension of this study is to measure the moderating impact of servicescape and personal interrelation on the internal marketing and internal customer satisfaction. Survey based data was collected from 210 employees of large retail stores of Pakistan using simple random sampling technique using close ended questionnaires. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data that was gathered. The results revealed that personal interrelation and servicescape moderate the relationship between internal marketing and internal customer satisfaction in a way that high level of personal interrelation and better servicescape make the relationship strong between internal marketing and internal customer satisfaction. While a significant body of prior research has established links between internal marketing and internal customer satisfaction, this is the first known attempt to evaluate the moderating impact of servicescape and personal interrelation on other study variables.

Keywords: Internal Marketing, Internal Customers, Personal Interrelation and Servicescape

Is Sustainability a Problem for the Next Generation? Social media marketing's Impact on Consumer Intention to Reduce Waste in the Hospitality Sector.

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the study is how social media marketing activities (SMMA) affect intention of the young consumers to act sustainably. Previous studies are related to household waste, management of solid waste, air pollution, and volume of solid waste generated in cities but the consumer intention towards food waste specifically when eating out in restaurants is rare. Therefore, this study is conducted in the context of Pakistan's hospitality sector, which has a crucial role in food supply chain towards the food waste.

This study used 449 young consumers as sample with convenience sampling. All hypotheses are evaluated related to independent factors (informativeness, interactivity, personalization, trendiness, and word of mouth) on the dependent variable intention to minimize waste through using the PLS-SEM approach.

The study found some intriguing results. With the exception of interaction and personalization, all three SMMA-related factors have been demonstrated to have a positive influence on young individuals' intent to minimize wasteful consumption. The study observed significant association of social media marketing with the development of intention among young consumers.

This study emphasizes the importance of sustainability, including social, economic, and environmental aspects, in understanding consumer behaviors. By using social media marketing restaurant's efforts to minimize food waste can be highlighted and improve the comprehension of young patrons regarding the consequences of waste.

Keywords: SMMA, Consumer Intention, Sustainability, Food Waste

Sustaining Innovation through Balance: Exploring Wellbeing and Performance in Technopreneurs

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The current study examined the impact of technopreneurs' work-life balance on their work well-being through their adaptive performance using Regulatory Focus Theory (Higgins et al., 1997).

Design/methodology/approach: This research study tested the hypothesized relationships using primary data collected from technopreneurs in Pakistan (n = 213) using self-administered questionnaires. The data time horizon for data collection was cross-sectional. Data screening, frequency analysis, One-Way ANOVA, reliability analysis, descriptive statistics, and correlation analysis were done in SPSS-21. All the direct and indirect effects were tested in PROCESS macro by Hayes (2017) using Model 4. All the proposed relationships among technopreneurs' work-life balance, adaptive performance, and work well-being were significantly positive.

Findings: According to this study, technopreneurs' ability to manage their work and personal life effectively allows them to adjust their behavior to the demands of the work environment, such as performing their work roles effectively and being responsive in the variable context, which ultimately leads them to experience overall quality at work.

Practical implications: This study gives insights that work-life balance is possible for technopreneurs, and they have a promotion focus (task accomplishment) and prevention focus (mistake avoidance) that makes them able to adjust their behavior according to the requirements of the environment they are in which helps them experience well-being at work. The findings can help employers understand the importance of working from home using technology and its role in the behavioral adjustment of technopreneurs of performing well and being responsive which results in experiencing well-being while at work.

Originality/value: This research study adds value to the literature by examining the effect of the work-life balance of technopreneurs on their work well-being through their adaptive performance. It highlights that it is easier for technopreneurs to balance their work and personal life.

Keywords: Technopreneurs, Work-life Balance, Adaptive Performance, Work Well-being, Regulatory Focus Theory

Leadership and Psychological Climate Synergy: Unveiling the Impact of Green Human Resource Management on Green Innovation in Fertilizer Sector

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ABSTRACT

Enhanced toxic emissions, environmental degradation and increase in pressure from stakeholders to opt green policies have led companies to come up with guidelines and strategies for environmental protection. Considering the growing environmental concern, this research intends to investigate the relationship between Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) and Green Innovation (GI). Psychological Green Climate mediates the association between GHRM and GI whereas Green Transformational Leadership is used as a moderator between GHRM and PGC. The data were gathered from 287 employees of fertilizer manufacturing companies that are listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. Using Smart PLS, structural equation modelling is applied for the analysis. The findings show that green HRM practices such as green training and development, green performance appraisal system, green employee empowerment, green job description help employees to develop a psychological understanding of the significance of sustainable policies, which will ultimately result in development of the products and processes which do not cause environmental harm (green innovations) in the fertilizer industry. This study is novel since this research framework has not been previously investigated in Pakistan's fertilizer industry; as the mediation of PGC has not

been examined yet between GHRM and GI. This study has significant implications for the fertilizer manufacturing businesses in developing countries such as Pakistan. This study will help fertilizer industry of Pakistan to lessen their carbon emission and save their resources through green innovation ultimately leading towards sustainable competitive advantage.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management, Green Transformational Leadership; Psychological Green Climate; Green Innovation; Fertilizer Industry

COMPUTER SCIENCE

Safeguarding the Skies: A Lightweight Blockchain and Real-Time Message Content Validation Framework for UAV Communication

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ABSTRACT

The use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) is growing in several fields, such as delivery and surveillance, search and rescue, and more. In terms of security, trust, and real-time data validation, UAV networks' decentralized structure presents substantial obstacles. The proposed approach makes use of blockchain technology to create a decentralized, impenetrable ledger for documenting UAV interactions and transactions. Secure and dependable communication between UAVs is ensured through the use of smart contracts, which automate and enforce pre-established norms and protocols. To further improve the system's overall security, a Real-time Message Content Validation (RMCV) approach is used to verify the authenticity and integrity of communications sent between UAVs. Extensive simulations were conducted to evaluate the performance of our framework, revealing significant improvements in various metrics. Notably, the RMCV system demonstrated a trustworthiness evaluation time of less than 0.8 seconds, even when processing up to 100,000 messages. Additionally, the transaction throughput of the blockchain system was observed to fluctuate with the number of UAVs, showing a decrease in throughput as the number of UAVs increased, although this decline became less pronounced at higher UAV counts. The results confirm the proposed model's efficacy in enhancing the security, dependability, and efficiency of UAV networks. The findings demonstrate that our strategy improves the overall quality of service for UAV applications, minimize communication delay, and dramatically lower the danger of cyberattacks.

Keywords: Blockchain, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, Real-time message Content Validation, Smart Contracts, Security

Semantic Modeling for the Detection of Software Design Flaws.

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ABSTRACT

Software design quality is critical in respect to overall quality and performance of the software. Poor design decisions regarding the violations of the best practices in software programming led to the generation of design smells, which afterwards affect software maintainability, extensibility, and performance. As software evolves to meet changing requirements, design smells tend to accrue, leading to what is termed "technical debt." Also, as source code changes over time, it deviates from its original design, introducing both technical debt and design smells. These smells violate object-oriented (OO) design principles, hindering maintainability and extensibility. Traditional detection methods focus on the implementation phase, leaving design-level issues to be discovered later in the development cycle, where they become costly to fix. In this paper, we propose an ontology-based approach that detects design smells at the design phase. Our research proposes the development of an ontology-enabled, semantic, machine-readable knowledgebase for detecting design smells, based on formal specifications of software design. We will model optimal OO design principles using the Web Ontology Language (OWL), with smell detection rules represented as axioms. An ontology reasoner will check for consistency to ensure that the defined constraints are met. Target systems will be evaluated against this knowledgebase to identify flawed designs. Our approach will be extensible, allowing for the detection of new design smells as they are formally defined, and it will be evaluated using open-source Java repositories. This work aims to help both researchers and practitioners detect design smells, improving software quality and preventing software erosion.

Judicial Case and Event Management System

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ABSTRACT

This study proposes the development of an advanced Judicial Case and Event Management System (JCEMS) to streamline the handling of extensive judicial data traditionally managed manually. The system will feature secure user login via email or phone, event listings with descriptions, access to past judgements categorized by court, year, and judge, and the ability to cite judgements as precedents. Users will be able to retrieve case information using various identifiers, submit new cases, and enable lawyers to take up cases based on their expertise. The platform will facilitate client-lawyer communication, case withdrawals, and profile creation for lawyers and interns. Additionally, it will provide case status updates and user support resources. This system aims to enhance the efficiency and accessibility of judicial data management, reduce administrative burdens, and improve the overall judicial process.

Keywords: Challenges; Accelerated construction; Modular construction; Prefabrication.

Optimizing CNN-Based Image Classification with Ensemble Models and Transfer Learning

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the application of Boosting Ensemble methodologies to improve the accuracy of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) on diverse image datasets, such as CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and Fashion MNIST. The central focus is on employing AdaBoost, a widely used boosting algorithm, to enhance the performance of the underlying convolutional neural network models. Additionally, the study explores AdaBoost's effectiveness in handling imbalanced datasets, providing insights into its potential to address class imbalances. The empirical results highlight AdaBoost as an effective complementary strategy for enhancing convolutional neural network accuracy, particularly in scenarios with imbalanced class distributions. Noteworthy is the fact that our ensemble model achieved a 6% higher test accuracy compared to the baseline convolutional neural network. These outcomes make substantial contributions to the ongoing research in ensemble learning and offer valuable insights for practitioners involved in image classification tasks.

Keywords: Convolution Neural Network, AdaBoost, Imbalanced Dataset, Transfer Learning

Enhancing Campus Security: The Development and Implementation of the "Campus Vigil Watch" Deep Learning Surveillance System

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the increased demand for heightened campus security has remained a critical concern, necessitating proactive measures to detect and respond to threats promptly. Traditional surveillance methods often fall short in detecting weapons or suspicious activities in large, complex environments like university campuses. In this study, we propose an innovative deep learning security solution named "Campus Vigil Watch," which employs Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) techniques to detect objects like guns and knives within a campus environment. CNNs are chosen for their effectiveness in image classification and feature extraction, crucial for identifying potential threats in video feeds. Campus Vigil Watch addresses this challenge by leveraging cutting-edge CNN models to enhance surveillance capabilities. Central to this effort is the integration of the Gemini API, which improves the system's ability to retrieve and analyze detailed information related to weapon detection alerts. In this study, we first performed the data collection process, ensuring the acquisition of diverse and representative datasets essential for training machine learning models. Efficient data collection involves capturing video feeds from various campus locations using networked cameras. This raw video data undergoes preprocessing steps to extract frames and annotate instances of guns and knives, forming the labeled dataset crucial for model training. To optimize

performance and resource utilization, advanced data reduction methods are implemented. Techniques such as data augmentation, which synthetically expands the training dataset, and feature extraction to focus on relevant regions within frames, enhance model efficiency. These strategies are crucial for maintaining the real-time processing capabilities necessary for effective surveillance and threat detection. The model will then be trained, and its performance will be evaluated using evaluation metrics. Additionally, the system includes practical applications through mobile and web interfaces. These interfaces, integrated with the Gemini API, provide security personnel with accessible and responsive monitoring tools, allowing real-time surveillance of campus areas. Alerts generated by the system prompt immediate responses to potential threats, facilitating proactive intervention and enhancing overall campus safety.

Keywords: Deep-learning, Computer Vision, Security, large language model, Gemini API

ENGINEERING

Smart Hybrid Bike

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ABSTRACT

The advent of smart technologies has paved the way for innovative solutions in the realm of transportation. This project introduces a groundbreaking concept—the development of a Smart Hybrid Bike that seamlessly blends traditional cycling with cutting-edge technology. The bike integrates a sophisticated smart monitoring and control system, incorporating sensors to monitor vital parameters such as speed, distance, temperature, and battery level. A user-friendly interface, accessible through a handlebar-mounted display or a mobile app, empowers riders to customize their biking experience and receive real-time feedback on various metrics. The usage of a GPS module integrates into the motorcycle fuel canteen, therefore sends directions of turns aside from tracking the distance that a rider goes. With its anti-theft mechanism that includes GPS tracking, one of the safest security items is not only the bike itself but also its rider for many decades, the traditional bike and petrol-powered option have ruled the streets of cities. It is a basic vehicle design and popular among urban dwellers. Traditional bikes with the combustion engine run on fossil fuels that power the vehicle. It is simple and reliable while resistant to alternative sources of power. However, bike is detrimental as it pollutes the environment and overuses the limited extraction of fuel. Consequently, millions of bike models have been used worldwide; the environmental damaging effort has sparked the search for an alternative.

Keywords: Transportation, Smart, Hybrid, Bike, Environment

Design and Development of IOT Based Solar Powered Building Energy Management System (BEMS)

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the IoT-Based Solar Powered Building Energy Management System (BEMS), addressing typical building issues like high energy consumption during peak hours and elevated electricity costs. It revolutionizes energy management by integrating solar power and IoT technology to optimize consumption and enhance efficiency. The system targets sustainable energy solutions for residential and commercial buildings by integrating solar energy and optimizing the load curve, especially during peak hours, through load scheduling and shifting. It minimizes thermal discomfort while optimizing load consumption, considering factors like temperature, humidity, and occupancy, with manual control via an app. An ESP32 microcontroller, charge controller, battery, solar panel, water tank motor, ultrasonic sensor, I2C module, voltage and current sensor, buck converter, and temperature and humidity sensor (DHT11) are some of the essential parts. The elements gather data in real time that is saved on Firebase. By alternating between solar and WAPDA power and controlling large load demands during peak hours, the system automates load management. To ensure optimal energy utilization, fan speeds and lighting are adjusted based on the number of people in the room. The energy efficiency of the system was found to have significantly improved, and users benefited from complete control and insights obtained from constant monitoring using an LCD display and a mobile app. The conclusion emphasizes how BEMS is a crucial development in sustainable building management systems because of its creative approach, which improves energy efficiency and gives users access to energy consumption and data monitoring.

Keywords: BEMS, BMS, IOT, ESP32, Automation, Microcontroller.

A Simulation-Based Driven Method to Design and Analysis of Wireless Power Transfer for Electric Vehicle Systems

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ABSTRACT

In this research, we designed and optimized the wireless power transfer (WPT) systems for electric vehicles (EVs) through an extensive simulation approach. We focused on three major factors: the distance between the transmission coils and receiver coils, the review of the configuration of these coils and compensation topologies in both coils. We discovered that power transfer efficiency was maximum when the coils were placed close together, confirming numerical analysis. The best performance was achieved with 1.5cm airgap between the coils, by reducing distance beyond this point yielded only marginal improvements. Furthermore, our simulations showed that by using Series-Series capacitor in both the transmitter and receiver coils helped achieve resonance eliminating reactance, enhanced the coupling coefficient and the power transfer efficiency. These results offer practical insights into optimizing WPT systems, suggesting that both minimizing distance, carefully designing coil configurations and configuring the capacitors in both coils are pivotal in improving power transfer efficiency.

Keywords: Electric Vehicle (EVs), Wireless Power Transfer (WPT), Compensation Networks, Series-Series Resonant Inductive Power Transfer (SS-RIPT)

Power Macro-modeling for Intellectual-Property (IP) based Multi-core MIPS processor Design

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ABSTRACT

Power consumption is a critical design constraint in electronics system design. It becomes more important in low-power systems. An increase in the complexity of a system is directly proportional to power consumption. Early power estimation is crucial in multicore design as it mitigates the risk of redesigning. This research proposes an improved model for power macro-modeling, utilizing random values with different statistical properties generated through the Enhanced Whale Optimization Algorithm (EWOA). A multicore 32-bit MIPS architecture serves as the test system. The model achieves an average percentage error of 7.45% in the multicore system. The results show that the power estimation model provides more accurate results than the previous model. The simulated and estimated power results are compared, and result validation is conducted through statistical error analysis. Statistical error analysis validates the accuracy of the proposed power macro-model, making it a reliable technique for early power estimation in complex systems.

Keywords: MPSoC, Power Macro-modeling, IP, Multicore, EWOA and Regression

Design and Control of Ball Balancing System

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ABSTRACT

The design and control of a ball balancing system pose a complex challenge in control engineering, requiring precision and real-time responsiveness. This paper presents the development and implementation of a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller to stabilize a ball on a plate using a resistive touch panel for real-time position sensing. Central to the system's operation is a resistive touch panel, which provides continuous, real-time feedback on the ball's position across both the X and Y axes. The data from the resistive touch panel is critical as it serves as input for the PID controller, enabling it to make precise adjustments to the motors that control the plate's angle. The design methodology focuses on developing a robust and responsive PID controller capable of dynamically adjusting to the ball's position on the plate. The controller processes the positional feedback from the resistive touch panel and computes the necessary corrections to maintain the ball's balance by manipulating the plate's tilt. The challenge lies in ensuring the controller's ability to quickly and accurately counteract any deviations, thereby keeping the ball centered. The effectiveness of the system is evaluated through rigorous testing under various conditions, including different initial positions of the ball and external disturbances. The novelty of this research lies in the comparative analysis of the resistive touch panel versus camera-based systems, evaluating factors such as response time, accuracy, and system robustness. Rigorous testing under various initial conditions and external disturbances revealed that the resistive touch panel outperforms camera-based systems in terms of efficiency, offering faster response times and enhanced reliability without the complexity of image processing. These results underscore the effectiveness of touch-based sensing, demonstrating its superiority in achieving stability with fewer resources. This study contributes to control system design by presenting a more efficient and streamlined alternative to traditional methods, with potential applications in automation and educational platforms.

keywords: Ball balancing, PID controller, Equilibrium, Automation, Dynamic Stabilization, Real-Time Control

A review of Hydrogel Based PH-Sensors

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogel-based sensors are of immense interest for their remarkable biocompatibility, flexibility, and adaptability. In this article, a comprehensive review has been given of various hydrogels used in pH sensing applications. Types of hydrogels applied in the pH sensing applications are discussed followed by different types of transduction mechanisms that are involved in the hydrogel-based pH sensors. The importance of hydrogel-based pH sensors using wearable and implantable sensor technologies for applications in various disease management is elaborated. Their industrial use is mentioned, such as food quality control, biomedical diagnostics, and environmental monitoring. The potential and the current challenges related to hydrogel-based sensor technologies are discussed in the final remarks, which are drawn from previous research contributions. Sensitivity, stabilizing the system, and biocompatibility are the critical areas of concern that underscore the demand for continued study. The hydrogel-based sensors have the potential for the revolution of sensing technology by overcoming these challenges. Such potential effects can have profound implications for a vast range of academic fields and commercial industries. This thorough analysis sheds light on the importance, uses, and range of hydrogel-based pH sensor types while offering insightful information on their adaptability and prospects in a number of domains. This study is a helpful resource for researchers and practitioners seeking novel sensing solutions by examining the many types and uses of these sensors.

Keywords: Biocompatibility, sensitivity, Hydrogel, Transduction, Implantable.

Innovative Pathways for Sustainable Fuel Production: Converting Bio-Crude into Renewable Petrol & Diesel

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ABSTRACT

Limited domestic resources, high fuel imports and finite access to modern fuel resulting in economic burden has led to increase in energy poverty in Pakistan. Moreover, waste management is the burning issue in the context of agricultural residue which is burned by farmers causing soil deterioration and air pollution. These significant and interconnected issues of the Pakistan that have far-reaching economic, environmental, and social implications. The primary goal of sustainable fuel production is to reduce the environmental and social harm associated with traditional fossil fuel extraction and production methods. Bio-crude is a liquid biofuel produced by thermochemical conversion of wide variety of biomass. Fast pyrolysis considered as an efficient and the most economical technique of valorization is used for the production of bio-crude from wheat straw. Catalytic upgrading methods like hydro-processing are then employed to upgrade biocrude to a variety of fuels including diesel and gasoline. In present work, techno-economical and environmental assessment is made for the process. Moreover, a complete process route is developed including process design, material and energy balances for optimum conditions with detailed economic analysis to determine its feasibility. With pyrolysis being the most inexpensive route towards biofuels, the developed process can serve as a solution towards energy crisis issues of Pakistan.

Keywords: Bio-oil, Pyrolysis, Hydrotreating, Hydrocracking, Product gas.

Green production route of 15000 tons per year of Acrylic Acid from Glycerol

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ABSTRACT

The rapid industrial and economic development runs on crudeoil-based raw materials. Limited oil reserves and environmental issues have pushed the industrial sector towards more sustainable raw materials such as Glycerol for Acrylic Acid production. Glycerol is currently being produced globally, mainly due to the increased biodiesel production and soap production (produce glycerol as a by-product). One ton of glycerol is obtained as a by-product for every nine tones of biodiesel produced. Glycerol's economic value has been reduced due to the excess supply, making it possible to utilize it in various other applications. Many studies have been performed to exploit this excess glycerol as a raw material for manufacturing new products like acrylic acid. This approach reduces soap industry waste and carbon dioxide emissions by offering a sustainable alternative to traditional propylene as raw material. The main objective of the work is to evaluate the potential of producing acrylic acid using glycerol derived from the biodiesel production process. The acrylic acid market in Pakistan consists almost entirely of imported products, and there is no industrial manufacturing unit in the country. This project proposes the manufacture of acrylic acid using an ecofriendly process, eventually making Pakistan self-sufficient in its production.

The analysis indicates that this approach has the potential for scalability, with an estimated production of 15,000 tons of acrylic acid per year. Material and energy balance were used to design and rate various equipment, then matched to common design values from the literature. Simulation of reactors is also carried out on Aspen Plus. This project also took into account environmental regulations. A HAZOP analysis was conducted for the raw m. The process was also subjected to an economic study, and the results indicate that the project is fiscally feasible. With a 3.8-year payback period and a positive present worth value, this project is the best investment. At the end of the project, readers can find detailed references and appendices to assist them with various standard tables and charts.

Keywords: Acrylic acid, biodiesel, Pakistan, Glycerol

Smart Helmet Technology for Enhanced Safety in Coal Mining: Real-Time Monitoring and Hazard Detection

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ABSTRACT

The mining sector has great difficulties in terms of safety criteria due to the hazardous environmental conditions that surround it, including high temperatures and harmful gases like carbon dioxide and methane. This project aims to suggest the design of a smart helmet combining innovative sensor technologies with traditional protective gear, thereby enhancing the safety of coal miners. Sensors in the smart helmet will include the DHT22 to track temperature and humidity and the MQ9 to identify possibly harmful substances. These sensors will constantly evaluate the ground around the miners, therefore providing real-time data. Should environmental elements exceed certain safety thresholds, the helmet will provide the wearer loud alarms and vibrations to inform them. This guarantees that they will be instantly aware of any potential hazards that could exist. A microcontroller will handle the sensor inputs and generate warnings as well. These characteristics will make the system reasonably affordable and user-friendly. By integrating these technologies into a piece of equipment that is already recognizable to miners, the smart helmet provides them with the ability to protect themselves from potentially hazardous circumstances by providing them with vital information. This progressive approach not only increases the personal safety of specific people but also promotes a safe culture across the mining industry. The main goals of the smart helmet project are to improve the general working conditions for miners and significantly reduce the frequency of accidents happening. This will enable them to perform their roles safely under demanding working conditions. With this initiative, we want to transform the accepted safety protocols used in the mining sector. Our aim is to ensure that miners can confidently and safely perform their challenging tasks.

Keywords: Coal Mining Safety, IoT (Internet of Things), Worker Safety, Hazard Detection, Real-Time Alerts, Environmental Monitoring.

IoT-Driven Smart Helmet: Redefining the Landscape of Motorbike Safety

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ABSTRACT

For bike riders on the road, safety is the primary concern. With the progress of technology, safety features will also increase to assure genuine safety and convenience in the lives of humans. Motorcycle accidents remain one of the top causes of death and serious injury all over the world leading to high casualties that can be dramatic and require timely safety measures for motorcyclists. This paper portrays the vivid design and development of a smart helmet that uses an advanced sensor technology approach for motorcycle safety by interfacing and enhancing helmets using real-time data acquisition. The smart helmet has a lot of sensor modules on board such as MPU-6050 (accelerometer and gyroscope) for accident detection, a NEO-8M GPS module to judge the exact location of the rider. The Smart Helmet innovative design which is equipped with smart sensors. It sends alerts to the App in the Phone when GSM lateral movement is detected, like when the rider's brain collides with the skull. IoT has become the most varied and inventive technology presently. With this sophisticated technology, we have produced unique and inventive helmets to assure the safety and convenience of bike commuters. With the aid of the most advanced technology, all objects are linked to the internet, which allows for the verification of real-time data on board. The clever IOT helmet is simple to wear, and motorcyclists feel much more secure when utilizing this smart, revolutionary helmet while traveling.

Keywords: Motorcycle Safety, Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), Accelerometer, Accident Detection, Emergency Notification, Real-Time Tracking, Wireless Communication, Rider Safety, Sustainability

Geotechnical Review of Geological CO₂ Sequestration

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ABSTRACT

Geological CO₂ sequestration offers a promising method for mitigating climate change by storing carbon dioxide in subsurface formations. This concise review highlights key geotechnical aspects, focusing on the selection and characterization of suitable sites, such as deep saline aquifers, depleted oil and gas fields, and unmineable coal seams. Essential factors like injectivity, capacity, and effectiveness are quantitatively evaluated to determine their feasibility for CO₂ storage. Geotechnical considerations include the analysis of pore pressure, in-situ stresses, and rock strength, ensuring the stability and integrity of storage sites. Advanced techniques for monitoring and verifying storage sites are covered, alongside modeling approaches to predict long-term CO₂ behavior. Risk assessment addresses potential hazards such as leakage and induced seismicity, with strategies for mitigation discussed. Brief case studies provide practical examples of successful CO₂ sequestration projects, illustrating their geotechnical attributes. The paper identifies key geotechnical properties such as high porosity and permeability, favorable cap rock integrity, and robust geomechanical stability as essential for improving CO₂ sequestration efficiency and safety. The potential for geological CO₂ sequestration in Pakistan is also briefly examined, highlighting opportunities in local geological formations. Future recommendations put emphasis on the need for improved characterization techniques and robust monitoring systems to ensure the long-term viability of geological CO₂ storage. This review underscores the critical role of precise geotechnical evaluations in facilitating effective CO₂ sequestration, essential for addressing global climate challenges.

Keywords: Geological CO₂ sequestration, Geotechnical engineering, Site characterization, Carbon storage

Evaluating the barriers to the adoption of AR/VR technologies in the Construction Industry of Pakistan using Fuzzy DEMATEL approach

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ABSTRACT

The construction industry in Pakistan faces numerous challenges in adopting advanced technologies such as Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR). Despite their potential to revolutionize construction practices through enhanced visualization, safety, and efficiency, the uptake of AR/VR remains limited. This research aims to identify and analyze the barriers hindering the adoption of AR/VR in Pakistan's construction sector using the Fuzzy Decision-Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory (DEMATEL) approach. By employing this methodology, the study will assess the complex cause-and-effect relationships among various barriers, providing a comprehensive understanding of the critical factors impeding AR/VR implementation. The research is currently in progress, involving data collection from industry experts and stakeholders, followed by the application of Fuzzy DEMATEL to prioritize and categorize the barriers. The expected outcome of this study will offer valuable insights and actionable strategies to overcome these obstacles, fostering the adoption of AR/VR in the construction industry. Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to the modernization and technological advancement of Pakistan's construction sector, enhancing its overall efficiency and competitiveness on a global scale.

Keywords: Augmented reality; Virtual reality; Construction barriers; Construction Industry.

EVALUATION OF BRACING SYSTEMS FOR A MULTI-STOREY STEEL BUILDING SUBJECTED TO MISSING CRITICAL COLUMN SCENARIO

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ABSTRACT

There have been many examples of buildings in the past that have been subjected to progressive collapse due to the failure of one or more critical columns e.g. the fall of the Twin Towers of the World Trade Center in 9/11. The city of Mirpur, AJK, lies in Seismic Zone 3, and many past earthquakes have damaged the city severely resulting in the progressive collapse of many buildings. The missing column scenario represents a critical column that has been damaged by any unexpected loading and could lead to the progressive collapse of the building. The goal is to use the Alternate Load Path Method to divert the load of the damaged column to the remaining members. This study focuses on the design of an irregular multi-storey steel building, specifically evaluating different bracing systems for such a building facing a missing column scenario. The Static Equivalent Lateral Force analysis is used for the study by using the ETABS software. By applying the missing column scenario, testing is done on three different bracing systems (Eccentric Bracing, Inverted V Bracing, and X-Bracing) to ensure the stability of the structure. The results of the different bracing systems are compared using total roof lateral displacement, Deflection, and Beam-Column capacity ratio as failure criteria. Based on these criteria, X-bracings are proved to be the most suitable type of bracings in providing Alternate Load Path and ultimately stabilizing the structure.

Keywords: Progressive collapse, Alternate load path method, Deflection, Beam-column capacity ratio, Bracing

ANCIENT FORTS, MODERN METHODS: EVALUATING THE REDESIGNED MORTAR OF RAMKOT FORT AZAD KASHMIR

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ABSTRACT

Ramkot fort was built in the medieval period by Sultan Ghayas-ud-Din. This fort is situated near Mirpur City in a peninsula surrounded by River Jhelum and is experiencing serious deterioration due to environmental and aging effects. There is a dire need to restore the fort so that the cultural identity and historical integrity should be preserved for future generations. Rehabilitating heritage sites helps foster community pride and strengthens local distinctiveness. This paper aims to evaluate the ancient mortar of Ramkot Fort Azad Kashmir. The ancient mortar was analyzed using modern techniques like acid dissolution, sieve analysis, XRD, and XRF. The techniques revealed that the mortar consisted of lime, brick powder, clay, and sand. A modern mortar was prepared and tested in terms of density, workability, ease of construction, and mechanical strength. The results revealed that the mortar was highly flowable and had a low density of the order of 1.8 to 1.9 grams per cubic centimeter. The 28 days compressive strength was 1.5 MPa. The redesigned mortar was compatible both with brick and stone masonry. The compressive as well as bond strength of re-designed mortar was comparable to that of the modern 1:4 cement sand mortar. Repairing the earliest heritage with an identical mortar as originally used warrants that the restoration respects the historical, structural, and esthetic values of the building. It holds the authenticity and integrity of the heritage site while guaranteeing that the restorations are consistent with the original materials and construction methods.

Keywords: Ramkot Fort Azad Kashmir, ancient mortar, modern design, evaluation, construction.

FLASH DROUGHT DETECTION AND RISK EXPOSURE IN PAKISTAN: A MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH WITH MULTIVARIATE INDICES.

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ABSTRACT

Global warming has disrupted the rainfall patterns, intensified droughts and particularly resulting in the occurrence of flash droughts. We evaluated the drought severity in Pakistan (1991–2022) using the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) and Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) both being the effective tools for Pakistan's arid and semi-arid climate. High-resolution satellite data ($0.25^{\circ} \times 0.25^{\circ}$) for precipitation, temperature, and evapotranspiration was utilized for monitoring. Our analysis discovered a severe drought period (1999–2002) with SPI and SPEI values of -1.6 to -2.0 , indicating disruptions in rainfall patterns. Additionally revealed a 2012 drought in some regions which was linked to high temperatures. Tharparkar (Sindh), parts of Balochistan, and Punjab districts were most affected. Our study put forward an increased frequency and intensity of flash droughts during Pakistan's critical spring–summer crop season, possibly impacting the previously unaffected areas. Rising temperatures and evapotranspiration are key drivers for flash droughts occurrence. Effective drought monitoring using SPI and SPEI is crucial for water resource management and future drought prediction efforts.

Keywords: Drought indices, Flash droughts, Pakistan, SPEI, SPI.

DESIGN OF A HYBRID POWER SYSTEM USING HOMER: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a case study of PM Colony Market-Wah Cantt has faced persistent challenges of interrupted power supply and poor access to electricity. To address these issues, diversification of energy resources is essential. This study aims to conduct a techno-economic analysis of a hybrid energy system designed to enhance electricity reliability, reduce electricity bills, and decrease demand on the grid in this commercial area. The study evaluated a single hybrid system scenario comprising various combinations of grid, solar PV, inverter, and battery storage. Cost calculations and solar PV load analysis were performed, and the HOMER Pro Microgrid model was employed to identify the optimal system configuration. The best system configuration included the grid, solar PV, inverter, and storage. Additionally, the impact of the 2022 inflation rate on the financial performance of the system was assessed, revealing significant increases in capital, replacement, O&M costs, and payback time. The proposed system's levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) is \$0.095/kWh, which is lower than the Wah grid's LCOE of \$0.11/kWh. Environmentally, the system could contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions. As a result, supermarkets and malls should consider investing in alternative energy generation to improve sustainability and energy security.

Keywords: Electric Load, Solar PV, Converter, Grid, HOMER

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF OVERALL HEAT TRANSFER COEFFICIENT FOR WATER AND NANOFUIDS IN PARALLEL FLOW CONFIGURATION

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ABSTRACT

Shell and tube heat exchangers are primarily used in power plants, chemical industry and HVAC systems owing to the effectiveness in transfer of heat between fluids. An experimental setup for shell and tube heat exchanger (H.X) has been fabricated to perform experimentation in accordance with standard. The present study has been carried out to determine the heat transfer rate (Q) and overall heat transfer coefficient (U) of a shell and tube heat exchanger using alumina oxide nanofluids and distilled water for parallel flow configurations. Nanofluids with a concentration of 0.22% passed through the tubes while water entered through the shell of the heat exchanger in parallel flow. Rotameters were used to regulate and monitor flow rates of 6, 8, and 10 liters per minute (LPM) and K-type thermocouples were used to measure temperatures at the inlet and outlet of the shell and tubes. The research compares these values against water in a parallel flow arrangement, with an emphasis on the heat transfer rate and overall heat transfer coefficient. The results show that, as compared to water, the nanofluid significantly enhances heat transfer rates by 22.56%, 14.51% and 10.25% for the flow rates 6, 8, and 10 LPM, respectively. Similarly, the overall heat transfer coefficient of nanofluids increased by 23.76%, 16.54%, and 12.35% at flow rate of 6, 8 and 10 LPM. These results highlight the improved performance of alumina nanofluid over distilled water in parallel flow.

Keywords: Parallel flow, STHX, Flow rates, Overall heat transmission coefficient, Heat transmission rate.

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